

Annex to the ECOPOTENTIAL first periodic report

SURVEY OF COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

Mariasilvia Giamberini, Simona Imperio, Biagi, Yrneh Ulloa

This report is an annex to the first periodic reporting of Work Package 12 of the H2020 R&I project ECOPOTENTIAL (Grant Agreement n. 641762). It is aimed to verify the implementation of the Communication and Dissemination plan (D12.4).

It contains:

1. The list of the communication activities reported in Table 1 of the C&D plan (D12.4) and the status of their implementation
2. The indicators of communication and dissemination performance (Table 2 of the C&D plan)
3. The survey of social media activities
4. The list of conferences and other dissemination events where ECOPOTENTIAL has been presented (either presentations of the projects as a whole and scientific results presentations).

1. List of activities from the C&D plan – status of implementation.

The status of implementation of the actions reported in “Table I: Summary of actions” of the Communication and Dissemination Plan (D12.4) has been checked.

The following actions have been undertaken:

- Project website design, implementation and maintenance with sections targeted at different audiences
- Quarterly newsletter
- Social Media (Facebook, Twitter) accounts setting and maintenance
- Science policy interface and experience sharing events/ communication material
- Standard ECOPOTENTIAL templates for partner use
- Visual tools put online via YouTube/Vimeo, etc.
- Print material (booklets, science papers reprints)
- Project deliverables
- Scientific Publications on Journals
- Presentations at conferences
- Science schools
- Internal communications (discussion board, email, teleconferences)

The actions that still are to be implemented or completed are:

- Photographic and museum exhibitions
- School workshops
- Science-policy study carried out in WP11 with strong communication component
- Citizen Science actions
- Public Discussion Forum

- ECOPOTENTIAL Virtual Laboratory Platform
- Community of practise (CoP)

The communication and dissemination activities undertaken may be summarized as follows (data uploaded in the EU Participant portal – System for Grant Management – Dissemination and Communication activities)

Table 1: Summary of communication and dissemination activities as reported in the EU reporting portal SyGMA

[Organisation of a workshop]	3
[Press release]	7
[Non-scientific and non-peer reviewed publications (popularised publications)]	3
[Flyers]	1
[Training]	3
[Social media]	2
[Web-site]	1
[Communication campaign (e.g radio, TV)]	3
[Participation to a conference]	48
[Participation to a workshop]	22
[Participation to an event other than a conference or workshop]	12
[Video/film]	2
[Participation in activities organised jointly with other H2020 project(s)]	1
[Other]	6

A further detail of the communication activities implementation is reported in the following table (From the C&D Plan – D12.4) and in the list of communication activities in Table 6 at the end of this document.

Table 2: Communication and Dissemination Activities from the C&D Plan

Action/tool	How to implement	Actions taken	Status of implementation	Further Actions
Project website with sections targeted at different audiences	Design, implement and maintain the website.	The website is active and it contains all the pages and information needed.	Actions due up to now implemented accordingly. Further actions will follow.	Update continuously and maintain web site security.
Quarterly newsletter	Quarterly issues to be released using a web content management system (e-mailing) and printed versions to be disseminated at conferences and events.	The CMS has been set up, the mailing list has been created and three issues have been released within the reporting period both via e-mailing and in printed version. A fourth issue has been released in December 2016.	Actions due up to now implemented accordingly. Further actions will follow as scheduled.	Release the newsletter quarterly.
Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	Set the accounts and promote actively the participation of the scientific community.	Facebook and Twitter accounts have been set up and are used regularly for advertising about project’s events.	Actions due up to now implemented accordingly. Further actions will follow as scheduled	Set LinkedIn account and ask partners to join it. Continuously update and use the social media.

Action/tool	How to implement	Actions taken	Status of implementation	Further Actions
				Enforce their use as a mean for disseminating information to the target audience.
Science policy interface and experience sharing events/ communication material	Organize meetings for science and stakeholders communication.	Awareness raising event "Putting mountains on the agenda of Horizon 2020" in Brussels, 25 April 2016.	Actions due up to now implemented accordingly. Further actions will follow as scheduled	Organization additional events at respective fora and platforms in the future depending on opportunities.
Standard ECOPOTENTIAL templates for partner use	Ensure a consistent brand is used by ECOPOTENTIAL partners in presentations and in publications.	A standard template was created and shared with partners for written reports, posters, banners and presentations.	Action completed	
Visual tools put online via YouTube/Vimeo etc	Disseminate ECOPOTENTIAL to different audiences.	Simple Show video produced and showed by November 2016. The Video has been displayed at the EASME EU Stand at the GEO plenary assembly in St. Petersburg, Nov 2016.	Actions due up to now implemented accordingly. Further actions will follow as scheduled	Further develop story maps over 2017 and disseminate the video.
Print material (booklets, science papers reprints)	Print and disseminate the leaflet	Leaflet produced by end June 2016 and distributed to all partners at General Assembly and major conferences and events (GEO BON, ESS, ILTER, Researchers Night)	Action completed	.
Photographic and museum exhibitions	Engage and educate with public exhibitions.	Planning / ideas development to occur in late 2016. Deliverable due month 30.	Due in-2017	To be planned and implemented in year 3 (month 30). Planning starts in late 2016.

Action/tool	How to implement	Actions taken	Status of implementation	Further Actions
School workshops	Educate young generation on the importance of nature to prosperous societies.	Established contacts with selected school teacher groups. Demo version of a scientific game released and tested.	Due in-2017	During the second year, specific activities will be planned and carried out.
Science-policy study carried out in WP11 with strong communication component	Raise awareness about bottlenecks and gaps in terms of integration of EO tools in decision making and management of PAs.	A comprehensive questionnaire was developed to identify the needs of PA managers for ECOPOTENTIAL research outputs, in close collaboration with assigned ECOPOTENTIAL scientific partners. Results are reported in D11.2.	First part of the study has been completed within D11.2.	D11.2, submitted in November 2016, reports the first results of the assessment. The report will serve as basis for the PA meeting in May 2017. Final report by month 42.
Project deliverables	Dissemination of results to wider research and practice communities, use and re-use of outputs.	The available deliverable open to the public are published on the website, section http://www.ecopotential-project.eu/2015-08-19-15-19-29/deliverables .	Actions due up to now implemented accordingly. Further actions will follow as scheduled	Upload public deliverables within one month after submission.
Citizen Science actions	Engage public in conducting science that helps the environment.	A methodology for a research program on citizen science in PAs has been developed for milestone 12.4. The methodology comprises both a survey on citizen science activities in protected areas and a PhD research-project on the potential of participatory research methods (like CS or PPGIS) for the assessment of cultural ecosystem services.	In progress	The milestone M12.4 (methodology for citizen science) has been implemented in month 18. It will be implemented according to WP12 Task 12.3 and D12.9 (month 36).

Action/tool	How to implement	Actions taken	Status of implementation	Further Actions
Scientific Publications on Journals	Disseminate knowledge and results to the scientific community.	10 papers have already been published on journals as an outcome of the project.	In progress	Scientific results will be submitted for publication by all research partners.
Presentations at conferences	Disseminate knowledge and results to the scientific community.	The project's outputs have been presented at more than 50 international events during the first year. The project as a whole has been presented at more than 20 events. Details are reported separately.	Actions due up to now implemented accordingly. Further actions will follow as scheduled	Scientific results will be submitted for presentations and posters by all research partners.
Science schools	Training of young researchers.	1 summer school in La Palma (Spain) 2 summer school in Valsavarenche (Italy)	Actions due up to now implemented accordingly. Further actions will follow as scheduled	2 further science schools scheduled at months 27 and 39.
Public Discussion Forum	Position ECO POTENTIAL scientists as leaders in the field, engage and educate members of all sectors, provide a channel for Science-Policy interface.	Participation to many of the several forums listed in section 5.2.2. (LTER, LifeWatch, Future Earth, EU-BON).	Actions due up to now implemented accordingly. Further actions will follow as scheduled	Participation to several forums
ECOPOTENTIAL Virtual Laboratory Platform	Provide open and unrestricted access to interoperable ecosystem Earth Observation data and information. Provide web-based services, open archives, scientific models, semantic assets, and analytics services. Contribute to GEO using the GEOSS Common Infrastructure.	Design of VLP architecture. A demo of the VLP prototype has been shown at the project General Assembly at the end of June 2016. First release and prototype of the platform has been released in June 2016. http://ecovrp.geodab.eu/ecopotential-vrp/home/index-dev.html	In progress	An advanced version will be released at the beginning of 3 rd year, the final release is planned during year 4.

Action/tool	How to implement	Actions taken	Status of implementation	Further Actions
Community of practise (CoP)	Develop a link with stakeholders such as PA managers, nature conservation associations, economic sectors and concerned citizen groups.	Close contacts with the PA managers of the PAs in the project. A 3 days workshop has been planned for May 2017. The programme has been established.	In progress	Meeting with the PA managers in ECOPOTENTIAL, to be expanded to the GEO community.
Internal communications (discussion board, email, teleconferences)	Ensure efficient information exchange, mutual support and foster scientific innovation.	Internal communication has been established, regular meetings are taking place and all the tools have been implemented.	Action completed	Partners responsible of the tasks are organising the internal communication due for sharing the duties. Monitor the efficiency of internal communication tools.

2. C&D performance indicators

The number of persons reached by Communication and Dissemination activities has been estimated as reported in the following Table 3, in order to be uploaded in the Participant’s Portal SyGMA technical reporting web site.

Table 3: Estimate of the number of persons reached by communication activities

ACTIVITY	INSERT A NUMBER	NOTES
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	4010	conferences: 9 general + 7 scientific; average 200 people reached per conference (some plenary sessions, some side sessions) WRKSPS=8 general, 7 scientific - average 50 people per workshop + 3*20 science school students
Industry	n.a.	
Civil Society	n.a.	
General Public	1200	5 presentations @ researchers' night - average 200 people per presentation + 200 school pupils in Thessaloniki - no data from tourists of Pas – we need to improve this when we will have more results, maybe with posters at the visitor centers
Policy Makers	184	80 end users (including directors) of PA WP11 survey + (8 @ESP, 8@meeting of Ghada, 8@GEOBON meeting)+ 5% of attendees at conferences (no workshops)
Media	6992	700 from press releases; web: 400 *5 mesi- newsletter: 300 facebook: 1657; twitter: 1722 + 548 Eu-factor video visualisations + 65 Ecop video visualisations
Investors	n.a.	
Customers	n.a.	
Other	n.a.	

Moreover, monitoring of Success of Communication Tools and Strategies has been planned in the Description of Actions and in the Communication and Dissemination Plan using an array of indicators as reported below. The choice of indicators will be revised in the next update of the C&D plan.

Table 4: Communication indicators as from Description of Actions and C&D Plan

Communication Tool	Metric of verification*	Result
Project website with sections targeted at different audiences	Visitors in each part of the site; Number of pages visited; Referral statistics.	The most visited 18 pages (in brackets the date of issue of the page) are: Partners (24/08/2015), 6781 accessi Mission (19/08/2015), 4285 accessi Contacts (24/08/2015), 3471 Coordination (19/10/2015), 2929 Presentations (06/10/2015), 2654 Mediterranean LME (26/08/2015), 2542 Hardangervidda (24/08/2015), 2399 Har Negev (20/08/2015), 2335

Communication Tool	Metric of verification*	Result
		<p>La Palma and Caldera de Taburiente (21/08/2015), 2154 Posters (19/10/2015), 1890 First ECOPOTENTIAL General Assembly (28/06/2016), 1886 Storylines (30/05/2016), 1886 Camargue (24/08/2015), 1863 Ohrid and Prespa (24/08/2015), 1834 Scientific Advisors (17/09/2015), 1825 Gran Paradiso (24/08/2015), 1774 Publications (30/03/2016), 1726 Deliverables (30/03/2016), 1676</p> <p>Other relevant statistics: (average per month): Number of sessions: 626 (424 users): 17.41% from Italy, 9.42% from Germany, 7.99 from Spain. Page visualisations: 2152; Page/session: 3.44 Session time: 00:03:21 % new sessions: 67.73% (Habitual users: 32.1%).</p>
Quarterly newsletter	Number of non-partner subscriptions for e-delivery.	Subscribers: 299 Partners: 111 (70.6%) Non partners: 88 (29.4%)
Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	Number of followers/members; Number of retweets.	Twitter: 233 Followers, 416 Tweets Facebook: 116 Followers
Research brochures / highlights / policy briefs	Number of downloads.	<p>The brochure and other communication documents have been distributed to partners via the internal communication platform and then the partners distributed the brochure via email / facebook pages, so the information that we have from the website is not complete.</p> <p>Anyway, the “brochure” webpage has been visited 964 times since the date of issue (04/07/2016) to Dec. 31st 2016. We estimate a download for each visit.</p>

Communication Tool	Metric of verification*	Result
Visual tools put online via YouTube/Vimeo, etc.	Number of views / other online metrics (e.g. average time spent watching).	On Facebook, Ecopotential video reached 1168 people. On YouTube, it has been seen 457 times. On Twitter, the video earned 666 impressions.
Print material (booklets, science papers reprints)	Number of print material distributed.	2,000 brochures have been printed. 1,000: partners are distributing them to stakeholders and at public events (e.g. Researchers night). All the attendees at the GEO BON conference in July 2016 received within the welcome package. 1,000: CNR is distributing them at major events including ILTER conference in South Africa. 200 printed copies of the newsletter have been distributed at conferences.
Project deliverables	Number of downloads.	Deliverables have been distributed to partners via the internal communication platform, so and the information that we can extrapolate from the website is not complete. Anyway, since the date of issue (30/03/2016) to Dec 31 st 2016 the deliverable webpage has been visited 1676 times.
External communications	Number of information events.	We counted more than 30 communication events other than presentations at conferences / workshops. The most relevant are: 1 stand at the ESS conference in Antwerp, Sept 2016 1 day of discussion in Ecopotential at the Mountain Forum in Bruxelles, Posters and video displayed at <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Researchers night (4 venues) - EU Stand at GEO Plenary (St. Peterburg, Nov. 2016) - EU Stand at the ESS Conference in Antwerp, Sept. 2016 Interviews released at EU-Factor (communication event of the EU) Press releases on web magazines
Internal communications	Participation in Basecamp.	237 people participate to the internal communication platform (Basecamp).

Communication Tool	Metric of verification*	Result
(discussion board, mail)		Basecamp hosts the following discussion groups: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - General - Coordination team - Communication team - 12 discussion group (1 for each work package)

3. Social Media activities

(Yrneh Ulloa, Bayeturh University, Germany)

The Facebook site of ECO POTENTIAL is operative since October 5th 2015, and in the last 18 months has collected 104 Likes/followers, more than 129 engaged users and a total reach of 1657 people (Fig.1, Fig.2). Major peaks of user engagement were during the 1st General Assembly of the Project, as well as the release of audiovisual material like the brochure, official video, among others. So far the Facebook site does not register negative feedback from its fans. The majority of the fans (67%) are located in Europe, principally Italy, Germany, Portugal and Spain. The remaining half of the fans are users located in many other countries in the world, which proves the impact of the dissemination strategy beyond Europe.

Figure 1. Accumulated frequency of “Likes per day” and “Daily engaged users” in Facebook. The Likes received reflects the number of followers. The Daily engaged users are the number of people who clicked, liked, commented on or shared ECO POTENTIAL posts on a daily basis. The time period of the graph displays the first 18 months of the project. Major peaks in the activity are visible around the dates of the 1st General Assembly (June 2016) and the release of audiovisual material in the last months of 2016 (October – November).

Figure 2. Daily total reach of the first 18 months of the project. The total reach is the number of unique people who sees the content of the Facebook page on a daily basis.

The Twitter account of ECOPOTENTIAL, under the user @ECOPOTENTIALprj, is active since October 2015. In the last months has tweeted over 400 Tweets and gained 226 followers; it has been included in 30 thematic lists by its followers (Fig.3). The audience of the ECOPOTENTIAL Twitter account is composed by the followers and by their related followers, meaning that the project reaches approximately 1722 people on a daily basis.

The main topics of the followers revolve around these keywords: research, environmental, project, European, observation, university, ecology and remote. Moreover, a network map indicates that some of the most connected users and hashtags to ECOPOTENTIAL are the Horizon 2020 initiative, ESA, #ecosystems services and #remotesensing, among others (Fig.4).

Figure 3. Number of tweets per month in the first 18 months period of the project (Source: TweetStats)

Figure 4. Map of the most connected users and hashtags to the ECOPOTENTIAL (Source: Mentionmap)

4. Web site statistics (2015-2016)

(Simona Imperio & Benedetto Biagi, CNR, Italy)

The first pages of the Ecopotential Website have been published in August 2015. Until now, 146 pages have been published and all of them have been visited at least 100 times. From the publication date to 31/12/2016 there have been a total of 159,925 single pages visits. The 20 most visited pages were:

N.	Name	Publication date	Visits
1	Partners	24/08/2015	6781
2	Mission	19/08/2015	4285
3	Contacts	24/08/2015	3471
4	Coordination	19/10/2015	2929
5	Presentations	06/10/2015	2654
6	Mediterranean LME	26/08/2015	2542
7	Hardangervidda	24/08/2015	2399
8	Har Negev	20/08/2015	2335
9	La Palma and Caldera de Taburiente	21/08/2015	2154
10	Posters	19/10/2015	1890
11	First ECOPOTENTIAL General Assembly	28/06/2016	1886
12	Storylines	30/05/2016	1886
13	Camargue	24/08/2015	1863
14	Ohrid and Prespa	24/08/2015	1834
15	Scientific Advisors	17/09/2015	1825
16	Gran Paradiso	24/08/2015	1774
17	Publications	30/03/2016	1726
18	Deliverables	30/03/2016	1676
19	European Projects Workshop on Earth observation 2016	09/06/2016	1556
20	Curonian Lagoon	19/08/2015	1529

“Deliverables” page has been visited 1676 times, while the “Brochure” page has been visited 964 times. In the last month (1-31 December 2016) the site hosted 626 sessions (from 424 users) for a total of 2152 page visits. Other statistics are shown below:

■ New Visitor ■ Returning Visitor

The user language (language settings of the browser used to access the site) was:

Language	Sessions	% Sessions
1. en-us	214	34.19%
2. it	54	8.63%
3. en-gb	47	7.51%
4. de	33	5.27%
5. fr	31	4.95%
6. es	30	4.79%
7. it-it	30	4.79%
8. pt-pt	22	3.51%
9. es-es	20	3.19%

While the following image and table show the user country:

Country	Acquisition			Behaviour		
	Sessions	% New Sessions	New Users	Bounce Rate	Pages/Session	Avg. Session Duration
	626 % of Total: 100.00% (626)	67.89% Avg for View: 67.73% (0.24%)	425 % of Total: 100.24% (424)	44.73% Avg for View: 44.73% (0.00%)	3.44 Avg for View: 3.44 (0.00%)	00:03:21 Avg for View: 00:03:21 (0.00%)
1. Italy	109 (17.41%)	67.89%	74 (17.41%)	36.70%	5.68	00:03:19
2. Germany	59 (9.42%)	79.66%	47 (11.06%)	40.68%	3.25	00:02:50
3. Spain	50 (7.99%)	68.00%	34 (8.00%)	60.00%	2.34	00:02:25
4. Russia	42 (6.71%)	23.81%	10 (2.35%)	28.57%	2.02	00:04:58
5. Belgium	41 (6.55%)	58.54%	24 (5.65%)	31.71%	4.71	00:07:17
6. Portugal	34 (5.43%)	67.65%	23 (5.41%)	50.00%	2.76	00:03:03
7. France	33 (5.27%)	66.67%	22 (5.18%)	51.52%	2.73	00:02:34
8. Greece	29 (4.63%)	82.76%	24 (5.65%)	37.93%	3.24	00:05:03
9. United States	28 (4.47%)	78.57%	22 (5.18%)	53.57%	3.36	00:00:45
10. United Kingdom	26 (4.15%)	76.92%	20 (4.71%)	34.62%	3.19	00:02:45

It is also possible to view where the traffic comes from:

- Direct (indicates visits where users navigated directly to the URL),
- Organic Search (indicates visits from organic –unpaid– search results),
- Social (indicates visits from social networks: Facebook, Twitter, etc.),
- Referral (traffic where users clicked a link from another site, excluding major search engines).

Default Channel Grouping	Acquisition			Behaviour		
	Sessions	% New Sessions	New Users	Bounce Rate	Pages/Session	Avg. Session Duration
	626 % of Total: 100.00% (626)	67.89% Avg for View: 67.73% (0.24%)	425 % of Total: 100.24% (424)	44.73% Avg for View: 44.73% (0.00%)	3.44 Avg for View: 3.44 (0.00%)	00:03:21 Avg for View: 00:03:21 (0.00%)
1. Organic Search	303 (48.40%)	75.25%	228 (53.65%)	45.54%	3.08	00:03:38
2. Direct	214 (34.19%)	67.76%	145 (34.12%)	49.07%	2.86	00:03:02
3. Referral	78 (12.46%)	52.56%	41 (9.65%)	32.05%	7.12	00:02:44
4. Social	31 (4.95%)	35.48%	11 (2.59%)	38.71%	1.71	00:04:22

Next graph shows the channels of the traffic during a sample day (15/12/2016):

Organic search is the major source of traffic for Ecopotential website, however Google Analytics was not able to detect which keywords have been used apart from “ecopotential” and “h2020 ecopotential” (other keywords were not provided).

Referral and social traffic are also a good channel. Here is the list of the first 25 sources:

Source	Sessions	% New Sessions
twitter.com	18	5.56%
ecovrp.geodab.eu	17	35.29%
motherboard.vice.com	9	0.00%
biogeo.uni-bayreuth.de	8	62.50%
jobs.ac.uk	7	57.14%
carpathianconvention.org	5	40.00%
reddit.com	5	60.00%
t.co	5	80.00%
es-partnership.org	3	100.00%
washingtonpost.com	3	0.00%
3.basecamp.com	2	0.00%
bayceer.uni-bayreuth.de	2	100.00%
deib.polimi.it	2	50.00%
l.facebook.com	2	100.00%
localhost:9095	2	50.00%
scent-project.eu	2	50.00%
amberhimescornell.com	1	100.00%
citizenscience.org	1	100.00%
collaboriamo.org	1	100.00%
creaf.cat	1	100.00%
dta.cnr.it	1	100.00%
eurac.edu	1	100.00%
igg.cnr.it	1	100.00%
lse.ac.uk	1	100.00%
m.vk.com	1	100.00%

Finally, the following figure illustrates the users flow, which shows that users access the website mostly from the home page. Other starting pages are the ones related to the partners (Partner description, Work packages), or to dissemination (Protected Areas, Video).

5. Attendance at conferences and other dissemination activities.

ECOPOTENTIAL project and its scientific results have been presented at a number of scientific and public events. All the events and presentations are listed in Tables 4 and 5.A, 5.B, 5.C below, grouped in these three categories:

- Presentations of the project as a whole (in the framework of WP1 – Task 1.3: networking activities)
- Scientific presentations
- Other events and dissemination activities

On the whole, during this first reporting period there have been 47 participation at conferences, 22 at workshops and 11 at other events. The project as a whole has been presented 26 times: at 11 scientific conferences (7 oral presentations and 4 posters) and at 12 scientific workshops (all oral presentations) plus other events. Researchers gave 36 presentations of scientific results at conferences (27 oral presentations and 9 posters) and 10 scientific presentations at workshops. Scientific results were also presented at other events, as other projects' meetings, invited seminars, master courses.

Also, a number of other dissemination activities have been undertaken, as participation at the Researchers' Night, organization of dedicated workshops, press releases, newsletters, videos, and many other web-based communication actions (see Tables 1,2,4). A joint stand with the H2020 project SWOS has been set at the ESP international conference in Antwerp, Belgium, Sept 19-23.

Table 5: Summary of presentations at conferences, workshops and other events.

Event	Ecopotential as a whole - oral	Ecopotential as a whole - poster	Scientific presentations- oral	scientific presentations- poster
conferences	7	4	28	9
workshops	12	0	9	1

other events	3		4	1
<i>Total ECOP presentation as a whole: 26</i>	22	4		
<i>Total ECOP scientific results presentations: 52</i>			41	11

ECOPOTENTIAL: Attendance at conferences

The following tables contain a list of:

- A) Oral presentations (and posters) of the project as a whole
- B) Oral presentations (and posters) of scientific results
- C) Other dissemination activities

A) Table 6. A - Presentations of the project as a whole (oral presentations and posters) – WorkPakage 12.1 (dissemination) + 1.4 (networking)

C = conference

W = workshop

E = other event

P = poster

O = oral presentation

Event	P / O	DATE	EVENT	PLACE	PRESENTER	TITLE	PROOFING DOCUMENT
C	O	June 3, 2015	EU BON General Meetings and Symposium, Cambridge, 1-4 June 2015	Cambridge	Carmela Marangi	ECOPOTENTIAL: improving ecosystems benefits through Earth observation	Marangi-Cambridge-EUBON meeting-1-4 June 2015.pptx
W	O	11-12 June 2015	Towards a sustainability process for GEOSS Essential Variables (http://www.gstss.org/2015_Bari/program.php)	Bari, Italy	Antonello Provenzale	ECOPOTENTIAL: improving ecosystems benefits through Earth observation	Provenzale_Bari_EV_2015.pptx
W	O	15 - 16 June 2015	9th GEO European Projects Workshop	Copenhagen, Denmark	Antonello Provenzale	ECOPOTENTIAL: improving ecosystems benefits through Earth observation	PROVENZALE-GEPW9-NEW.pdf

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E	O	23 July 2015	LifeWatch-ECOPOTENTIAL meeting at CNR, Department of Earth and Environmental Science	Rome, Italy	Antonello Provenzale	H2020 ECOPOTENTIAL: improving ecosystems benefits through Earth observation	LifeWatch_Roma_2015_Prov.pptx
C	O	2-4 sept 2015	Pianeta Dinamico Congresso congiunto SIMP-AIV-SoGel-SGI	Florence, Italy	Antonello Provenzale	Poster: H2020 ECOPOTENTIAL: improving future ecosystems benefits through Earth observation	dynamicplanet_ecopotential.pdf
C	O	21-25 Sept 2015	13th European Ecological Federation (EEF) and 25th Italian Society of Ecology's (SIte) joint conference: "Ecology at the Interface in Rome"	Rome, Italy	Antonello Provenzale	ECOPOTENTIAL: improving ecosystems benefits through Earth observation	provvenzale_eef_plenary_small.pdf
C	P	11-12 November 2015	GEO-XII Plenary meeting	Mexico City	EU Commission Booth	POSTER: H2020 Project ECOPOTENTIAL: improving ecosystems benefits through Earth observation	GEOXII-ECOPOTENTIAL.pdf Mexico-Ecopotential.pdf
W	O	14 Nov 2015	IV convegno GPSO – ANP "La fauna del Piemonte"	Cherasco (CN) - Italy	Antonello Provenzale	Cambiamenti climatici e risposta degli ecosistemi (in Italian)	Provenzale_Cherasco.pdf
C	O	19-20 Nov 2015	Rome 2015 – Science Symposium on climate	Rome, Italy	Mariasilvia Giamberini	ECOPOTENTIAL: improving ecosystems benefits through Earth observation	Rome2015-final-SG.pdf
W	O	15 dic 2015	Conference: I sentieri dell'Acqua di Pianosa (in Italian)	Portoferraio (Italy)	Antonello Provenzale	Monitoraggio degli ecosistemi: progetti in corso e prospettive future (Italian)	Provenzale_Pianosa.pptx
W	O	20-21 Jan 2016	EC GEO European Projects Special Biodiversity Workshop	Brussels (BE)	Stefano Nativi, Paolo Mazzetti	ECOPOTENTIAL: Data portals, community portals, platforms, and GEOSS/GCI	ECOPOTENTIAL_WP10_2016-01-20_Brussels.pdf

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W	O	20-21 Jan 2016	EC GEO European Projects Special Biodiversity Workshop	Bruxelles	Antonello Provenzale	ECOPOTENTIAL: improving ecosystems benefits through Earth observation	ECOPOTENTIAL_Brussels_Jan2016.pdf
C	O	17–22 April 2016	European Geosciences Union General Assembly 2016	Vienna, Austria	Antonello Provenzale	ECOPOTENTIAL: improving ecosystems benefits through Earth observation	P_ECOP_EGU2016_Prov.pdf
Organisation of an event	E	April 25 th 2016	Mountains for Europe's Future: Putting Mountains on the Horizon 2020 Agenda (see http://www.chat-mountainalliance.eu/en/about-brussels.html). Plenary session	Brussels, BE	Matthias Jurek (UNEP), Sylvie Motard (UNEP), Piotr Mikolajczyk (GRID Warsaw)	Organized ECOPOTENTIAL side event at the margins of this Conference on mountain research	DRAFT PROGRAMME.pdf Mountains_for_Europe_Future_detailed_programme_v8_incl_Ecopotential.pdf
W	O	April 25 th 2016	Mountains for Europe's Future: Putting Mountains on the Horizon 2020 Agenda	Brussels, BE	Elisa Palazzi	ECOPOTENTIAL: improving ecosystems benefits through Earth observation	Programme: Mountains_for_Europe_Future_detailed_programme_v8_incl_Ecopotential.pdf
W	O	10 May 2016	ENVRI (Environmental Research Infrastructure) Community meeting	Zandvoort, Netherlands	H. Hummel	The role of MARS, EMBOS and EcoPotential (invited lecture)	Hummel - summary MARS EMBOS EcoPotential.ppt
W	O	May 31-June 2nd 2016	10th GEO European Projects Workshop 2016: Fostering Open Earth Observation for Europe	Berlin (DE)	Antonello Provenzale	ECOPOTENTIAL: improving ecosystems benefits through Earth observation	GEPW10_ECOPOTENTIAL_2-Prov-LR.pdf

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W	O	19-21 July 2016	4th SCERIN (South Central and Eastern European Regional Information Network) Capacity Building Workshop (CBW)	Zvolen, Slovakia	Ioannis Manakos	Improving future ecosystem benefit through Earth observation in the SCERIN: the Ecopotential approach (oral presentation)	manakos_SCERIN_ECOPOTENTIAL_web-july-2016.pdf
C	P	11-15 Sept 2016	EMC 2016 – Second European Mineralogy Conference	Rimini (Italy)	Chiara Boschi	Poster: Carbon Cycle and the geosphere-biosphere interactions	Posters_IGG_EM2016
C	O	9-13 Oct 2016	ILTER 1st Open Science meeting	Skukuza – South Africa	Antonello Provenzale	H2020 Project ECO POTENTIAL: making best use of remote sensing and in-situ observations to improve future ecosystem benefits	ECOPOTENTIAL2016_ILTER.pdf
C	O	9-13 Oct 2016	ILTER 1st Open Science meeting	Skukuza – South Africa	Antonello Provenzale	GEO ECO: The GEO Global Ecosystem Initiative (Presentation of the GEO-ECO initiative)	Proposal_GEO_ECO_ILTER
C	P	9-13 Oct 2016	ILTER 1st Open Science meeting	Skukuza – South Africa	Antonello Provenzale et al.	POSTER: H2020 Project ECO POTENTIAL: making best use of remote sensing and in-situ observations to improve future ecosystem benefits	Ecop_ILTER-GENERAL.DEFINITIVO.pdf
E	E	17. Nov. 2016	4th EU BON Stakeholder Roundtable	Berlin, Germany	Carl Beierkuhnlein (UBT); Piotr Mikołajczyk (GRID-Warsaw); Carlos Guerra (IdV)	[Piotr Mikołajczyk - participation in an interactive group discussion on monitoring and forecasting, tools for critical biodiversity assessment.]	participant List EU BON Roundtable v5.pdf (+minutes)

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E	O	16 Nov 2016	GIS Day @ University of Bergen	Bergen, NO	Tessa Bargman	ECOPOTENTIAL: improving ecosystem benefits through Earth observation	Bargman_GISdag_Nov-2016.pptx
W	O	14-17 November 2016	First “Life-EcoPotential” meeting on “Ecosystem management of protected areas”	Irvine, USA	Antonello Provenzale	ECOPOTENTIAL: improving ecosystem benefits through Earth observation	Provenzale_ECOPOTENTIAL-Nov-2016_Irvine-USA.pptx
Organisation of a workshop	E	14-17 November 2016	First “Life-EcoPotential” meeting on “Ecosystem management of protected areas”	Irvine, USA	CNR	Event: Joint Research Meeting ECO-Life	LIFE_ECO_Agenda_Final.pdf
C	P	November 16-17, 2016	LTER-Italy Congress and Assembly, 16-17 November 2016	Mantova (Italy)	Simona Imperio	H2020 Project ECOPOTENTIAL: making best use of remote sensing and in-situ observations to improve future ecosystem benefits (Poster)	LTER_Ecop_GENERAL.pdf
W	O	22-23 November 2016	9 th Regional meeting of the Technical Working Group – Water Framework Directive: From Planning to Acting – Transboundary Water Management Revisited	Tirana, Albania	Orhideja Tazevska	ECOPOTENTIAL: improving ecosystem benefits through Earth observation	PresentationECOP - RTWG Meeting in Albania.ppt

B) Table 6. B - SCIENTIFIC PRESENTATIONS AND POSTERS AT CONFERENCES AND WORKSHOPS

Event	O / P	DATE	EVENT	PLACE	PRESENTER	TITLE	PROOFING DOCUMENT
C	P	23 October 2015	1st International Symposium: What can remote sensing do for the conservation of Wetlands?	Seville, Spain	Pere Serra Ruiz, Alaitz Zabala, Xavier Pons, Javier Bustamante, Ricardo Díaz-Delgado, Antonello Provenzale	POSTER: ECOPOTENTIAL: a framework to monitor ecosystem services in protected wetlands with remote sensing.	Serra Ruiz-RSCW2015-abstract.pdf Available at http://ocs.ebd.csic.es/index.php/RSW/RSCW2015/paper/view/326
C	P	14-18 Nov 2015	AGU Fall Meeting 2015	San Francisco (USA)	Emiliana Valentini, Andrea Taramelli et al.	POSTER: Deltaic margins vulnerability: the role of landscape patches in flood regulation and climate adaptation	Poster_AGU_Fall_2015_v5.pdf
C	O	19-20 Nov 2015	Rome 2015 – Science Symposium on climate	Rome, Italy	Simona Imperio	Climate change effects on the distribution of large mountain herbivores	Imperio_Rome2015 - Science Symposium on Climate_19-20 November 2015.pdf
E	O	December 11, 2015	3rd EU BON Stakeholder Roundtable 10th – 11th December 2015, Granada, Spain	Granada	Carmela Marangi	"EO data for ecosystem modelling and monitoring"	Marangi-Granada-EUBON stakeholder roundtable 10-11 Dec 2015 .pdf
C	O	1-4 March 2016	7th European Coastal Lagoon (ECoLag) Symposium	Murcia, Spain	H. Hummel	Coastal lagoons in the framework of biodiversity observation networks (keynote lecture)	Hummel-March 2016-Eurolag-Murcia Spain-Keynote lecture.pdf Hummel-March2016-Eurolag-Murcia Spain-

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Event	O / P	DATE	EVENT	PLACE	PRESENTER	TITLE	PROOFING DOCUMENT
							round table summary.pdf
C	O	1-4 March 2016	7th European Coastal Lagoons Symposium,, Murcia	Murcia, Spain	Rutger De Wit (CNRS, Montpellier)	Oral Presentation: A. Leruste, S. Villéger, N. Malet, R. De Wit & B. Bec. First use of multidimensional functional diversity indices for phytoplankton in coastal lagoons	Eurolag7.27.02.16
C	O	1-4 March 2016	7th European Coastal Lagoons Symposium,, Murcia	Murcia, Spain	Rutger De Wit (CNRS, Montpellier)	Oral Presentation: R. De Wit. Restoration ecology for coastal lagoons : need for a highly integrated multidisciplinary approach	DeWit_7Eurolag.pdf
C	O	18th-19th April, 2016	NASA LCLUC Spring Science Team Meeting, 2016 (20th Anniversary) - Session – IX. International Partner Programs, Education and Capacity Building	Bethesda, Maryland (USA)	Ioannis Manakos	Earth Observation LULC products in support of Ecosystems monitoring in the EU (oral presentation)	Agenda-LCLUC_Ver.5.6_0.pdf manakos_NASA_LCLU C_springMeeting2016_web_sub.pdf
C	P	18th-19th April, 2016	NASA LCLUC Spring Science Team Meeting, 2016 (20th Anniversary) - Session – IX. International Partner Programs, Education and Capacity Building	Bethesda, Maryland (USA)	Ioannis Manakos	POSTER: Remote Sensing in service of ecosystems and human well-being	Ecopotential_Manakos_etal_NASA_LCLUC_sub.pdf
C	O	17–22 April 2016	European Geosciences Union General Assembly 2016	Vienna, Austria	Ghada El Serafy Sandra Gaytan Aguilar, and Alexander Ziemba	Improving the spatial and temporal resolution with quantification of uncertainty and errors in earth observation data	abstract-EGU2016-9454-El-Serafy-21-april-2016.pdf

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Event	O / P	DATE	EVENT	PLACE	PRESENTER	TITLE	PROOFING DOCUMENT
						sets using Data Interpolating Empirical Orthogonal Functions methodology	EGU-2016_DINEOF-Ziemba.pptx
C	O	17–22 April 2016	European Geosciences Union General Assembly 2016	Vienna, Austria	Antonio J. Pérez-Luque et al	Temporal trend of the snow-related variables in Sierra Nevada in the last years: An analysis combining Earth Observation and hydrological modelling	EGU2016-Sierra Nevada-April-2016pdf.pdf
C	O	20–23 April 2016	X Italian Congress of Mammalogy	Acquapendente (VT), Italy	Simona Imperio et al.	Factors affecting demographic parameters of an Alpine chamois population and estimated response to expected climate change	Imperio_Congresso Italiano di Teriologia_20-23 April 2016.pdf
W	O	April 25 th 2016	Mountains for Europe's Future: Side event dedicated to ECOPOTENTIAL	Brussels, BE	António Monteiro	ICETA : “Case study – Peneda-Gerês National Park, Portugal”	Programme: Mountains_for_Europe_Future_detailed_programme_v8_incl_Ecopotential.pdf
W	O	April 25 th 2016	Mountains for Europe's Future: Side event dedicated to ECOPOTENTIAL	Brussels, BE	Ana Stritih	Comparing mountain ecosystem services in protected and non-protected areas: The Swiss National Park and the region of Davos	Programme: Mountains_for_Europe_Future_detailed_programme_v8_incl_Ecopotential.pdf
W	O	April 25 th 2016	Mountains for Europe's Future: Side event dedicated to ECOPOTENTIAL	Brussels, BE	Piotr Mikolajczyk	Case study – High Tatras Mountains, Carpathians	Programme: Mountains_for_Europe_Future_detailed_programme_v8_incl_Ecopotential.pdf

Event	O / P	DATE	EVENT	PLACE	PRESENTER	TITLE	PROOFING DOCUMENT
W	P	6 - 7 May 2016	2 nd EARSeL SIG LU/LC and NASA LCLUC joint Workshop “Advancing horizons for land cover services entering the big data era”	Prague, Czech Republic,	Ioannis Manakos	POSTER: Multi modal knowledge based generation from remote sensing very high resolution imagery for habitat mapping OPEN ACCESS PAPER (gold): I. Manakos, E. Technitou, Z. Petrou, O. Karydas, V. Tomaselli, G. Veronico, G. Mountrakis, "Multi-modal knowledge base generation from very high resolution satellite imagery for habitat mapping", 2016, European Journal of Remote Sensing, (accepted for publication - to appear).	manakos_etal_WS_Prague_poster_prefinal.pdf
W	O	6 - 7 May 2016	2 nd EARSeL SIG LU/LC and NASA LCLUC joint Workshop “Advancing horizons for land cover services entering the big data era”	Prague, Czech Republic	Palma Blonda, ISSIA CNR – Bari	LC taxonomies for applications to biodiversity and ecosystems monitoring	Keynote_Blonda_PRA GA_2016.pdf
C	P	9-13 May 2016	ESA Living Planet Symposium 2016	Prague, Czech Republic	Dimitris Poursanidis	POSTER: Monitoring land cover changes over National Parks with EO to identify ecosystem functions, services and assist biodiversity conservation	POSTER: FORTH_2016_SAMARIA changes.pdf ABSTRACT: LPS16-poursanidis-7-may-2016-abstract.pdf

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Event	O / P	DATE	EVENT	PLACE	PRESENTER	TITLE	PROOFING DOCUMENT
C	O	9-13 May 2016	ESA Living Planet Symposium 2016	Prague, Czech Republic	Dimitris Poursanidis et al.	Monitoring land cover changes over National Parks†with EO to identify ecosystem functions” services and assist biodiversity conservation	Living Planet Symposium 2016 - ECO POTENTIAL.pdf ABSTRACT-
C	P	9-13 May 2016	ESA Living Planet Symposium 2016	Prague, Czech Republic	Emiliana Valentini	POSTER and Paper: Marine food provision ecosystem services assessment using EO products	POSTER: 2016_Valentini_et_al_Marine_Food_Provision_ES_using_EO_ESA_LPS2016_1942_poster.pdf
W	O	May 31-June 2nd 2016	10th GEO European Projects Workshop 2016: Fostering Open Earth Observation for Europe	Berlin (DE)	Hermann Hummel	Marine dimensions of European biodiversity and ecosystem observations	GEPW10_Hummel-marine biodiversity observation networks.pdf
E	P	June 2016	DEVOTES-Euromarine Summer School: Marine ecosystem services, management and governance: linking social and ecological research	San Sebastian, Spain	O.A. Hummel	The importance of Ecosystem Functions and Ecosystem Services to enhance the protection level of current and future Protected Areas	The importance of Ecosystem Functions and Ecosystem Services.pdf
C	O	3-8 July 2016.	51th Annual Congress of the Grassland Society of Southern Africa (GSSA)	George, South Africa	Abel Ramoelo (CSIR)	Oral Presentation: Towards earth observation based near-real time estimation of regional grass biomass as an indicator of rangeland quantity: A critical input for determining carrying capacity of herbivores	Biomass - Presentation-AR-Final-ECO.pptx
C	O	4 - 8 July	GEO BON Open Science Conference & All Hands Meeting.	Leipzig, Germany	Palma Blonda	Oral Presentation: A. Adamo, C. Tarantino, V.	Blonda_GEO_BON_LI PSIA_4_July_habmap

Event	O / P	DATE	EVENT	PLACE	PRESENTER	TITLE	PROOFING DOCUMENT
						Tomaselli, G. Veronico, H. Nagendra, P. Blonda. Pattern zonation rules and very high resolution satellite imagery for ecosystem extent monitoring	ping.pdf - presentation
C	O	4 - 8 July	GEO BON Open Science Conference & All Hands Meeting.	Leipzig, Germany	Ilse Geijzendorffer, Anis Guelmami, Gaetan Lefebvre, Brigitte Poulin	Oral presentation: Measuring ecosystem services variables in Mediterranean Wetlands	Abstract – OK GEOBON_Abstract_Book_OSC2016.pdf – S6.8
C	O	4-8 July	GEO BON Open Science Conference & All Hands Meeting.	Leipzig, Germany	Carlos Guerra:	Policy impacts on regulating Ecosystem Services	GEOBONconf2016-Guerra.pdf
C	O	4-8 July	GEO BON Open Science Conference & All Hands Meeting.	Leipzig, Germany	Evangelia Drakou	a. Mapping cultural marine ecosystem services from space: fact or fiction?	GEOBON_Abstract_Book_OSC2016.pdf S6 Drakou.pdf
C	O	4-8 July	GEO BON Open Science Conference & All Hands Meeting.	Leipzig, Germany	Domingo Alcaraz Segura et al.	Remotely-sensed Ecosystem Functional Types: monitoring functional diversity at the ecosystem level	Abstract: GEOBON_Abstract_Book_OSC2016.pdf S1.7 – Ecopotential is mentioned Presentation: Alcaraz-Segura_2016_GEOBON_ppt.pdf
C	O	4-8 July	GEO BON Open Science Conference & All Hands Meeting.	Leipzig, Germany	Ana Stritih	Bayesian modelling of mountain ecosystem services: A prototype for avalanche protection	Ana-Stritih-GEO-BON-4-7-2016.docx Abstract-Stritih_GEOBON-4th-july-2016.pdf – presentation

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Event	O / P	DATE	EVENT	PLACE	PRESENTER	TITLE	PROOFING DOCUMENT
W	O	6-9 September 2015	Estuarine Coastal Shelf Science Association (ECSA 55), London, UK	London, UK	Rutger De Wit (CNRS, Montpellier)	Oral Presentation: R. De Wit, A. Hervé, E. Romet, M. Ribot, J. Picot, L. Foulc, O. Loste, M. Thibault, O. Boutron, P. Grillas, B. Poulin. Offered space for coastal change in S. France; what to do with abandoned solar salterns?	ECSA_London_presentationDeWIT.pdf
E	O	15 September	Invited seminar at University of Brest	Brest, France	Ilse Geijzendorffer	Oral presentation: Ecosystem services and Sustainable Development Goals	Geijzendorffer SDGs 20160915
C	O	19-23 Sept 2016	European Ecosystem Services 2016 Conference	Antwerp, Belgium	Mariasilvia Giamberini, Ilaria Baneschi, Orhideia Tazevska et al	An Ecosystem Services Approach for the Sustainable Management of Lake Ohrid	ESS-conference-B3-Lake-Ohrid_Giamberini_Tazevska.pdf + email-acceptance
C	O	19-23 Sept 2016	European Ecosystem Services 2016 Conference	Antwerp, Belgium	Domingo Alcaraz Segura et al	Essential social-ecological functions to refine the conceptual framework of ecosystem services	PRESENTATION: Pacheco-Romero_EESC 2016 ppt.pdf (CONTAINS ONLY THE ECOP LOGO) Abstract: Pacheco-Romero_EESC 2016 abstract.pdf
C	O	19-23 Sept 2016	European Ecosystem Services 2016 Conference	Antwerp, Belgium	Arjen Boon, Alex Ziemba	Applying ecosystem services to optimize protected area management	abstract_ecopotential_Sevilla.docx presentation: 04-Boon+ElSerafy.pdf
C	O	19-23 Sept 2016	European Ecosystem Services 2016 Conference	Antwerp, Belgium	Herman Hummel	The importance of Ecosystem Services	The importance of Ecosystem Services

Event	O / P	DATE	EVENT	PLACE	PRESENTER	TITLE	PROOFING DOCUMENT
						required to qualify and install Marine Protected Areas – variable views of stakeholders and a comparison with other geographic domains http://www.esconference2016.eu/86157/subscribe?survey_id=69574&survey_key=CdjFot17PaYJB3tmg3xqShJODU0MTc0CkxMDAwCnRwMQou	required to qualify and install Marine Protected Areas – variable views of stakeholders and a comparison with other geographic domains - Herman Hummel.pdf Abstract
C	O	19-23 Sept 2016	European Ecosystem Services 2016 Conference	Antwerp, Belgium	Ricardo Moreno Llorca	Temporal evolution of ecosystem services in Sierra Nevada (Spain).	Abstract: Temporal evolution of ecosystem services in Sierra Nevada (Spain).pdf
C	O	19-23 Sept 2016	European Ecosystem Services 2016 Conference	Antwerp, Belgium	Simona Imperio, Tessa Bargmann et al.	Dynamics of high-altitude environments as a life-support system to wild herbivores: a storyline from the ECOPOTENTIAL project	Imperio_EESC_2016_Iow.pptx Abstract_EESC_high-altitude environments_Imperio.pdf
C	O	19 - 23 September	European ESP conference	Antwerp, Belgium	Ilse Geijzendorffer, Carlos Guerra	Oral presentation: Ecosystem services and Sustainable Development Goals	Geijzendorffer SGs abstract 20160919.pdf
C	O	26-30 September 2016	51st European Marine Biology Symposium (EMBS)	Rhodes, Greece	H. Hummel, J. van der Meer, O. Hummel et al.	The role of ecosystem functions and ecosystem services in the protection of protected areas	Hummel-27 Sept 2016-Rhodes Greece-51st EMBS .pdf

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Event	O / P	DATE	EVENT	PLACE	PRESENTER	TITLE	PROOFING DOCUMENT
E	O	Sep 25-26, 2015	European Researchers' Night (MeetMeTonight)	Milan, Italy	Renato Casagrandi (PoliMI)	Oral presentation: Big Data - Unexpected opportunities for Environment and Health	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9zUSfGL42mQ
C	P	9-13 Oct 2016	ILTER 1st Open Science meeting	Skukuza – South Africa	Simona Imperio et al.	POSTER: Long-term monitoring of two mountain ungulates in the Alps: ecosystem and cultural services, and impact of global changes	Ecop_ILTER-2016_ungulates.pptx
C	P	9-13 Oct 2016	ILTER 1st Open Science meeting	Skukuza – South Africa	Ramona Viterbi, Mariasilvia Giamberini, Ilaria Baneschi et al.	POSTER: Set-up of a long-term study on the changes in Alpine grasslands owing to climate and grazing pressure modifications	Ecop_ILTER-2016-grassland_DEFINITIVO.pptx
C	P	9-13 October 2016	1st ILTER Open Science Meeting	Skukuza, Kruger National Park, South Africa	Abel Ramoelo (CSIR)	Poster Presentation: Ramoelo A, Cho M.A. Towards earth observation based near-real time estimation of regional grass biomass as an indicator of rangeland quantity	ILTER 2016 KNP Ramoelov2_final.pptx
E	O	11 October	Invited teacher during a master course for practitioners at the Aix-Marseille university	Marseille, France	Ilse Geijzendorffer	Oral presentation: Zones humides Méditerranéens	Geijzendorffer zones humides 20161010.pdf
C	O	11-12 Oct 2016	ISSI FORUM - "Monitoring coastal zones evolution under various forcing factors using space-based observing systems"	Bern - Switzerland	Andrea Taramelli	Oral presentation: Living deltas and use of EO data: investigate a rapidly developing	Presentation: ISSI_Living delta_Bern_11_10_2016_final.pdf – ECOP is

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Event	O / P	DATE	EVENT	PLACE	PRESENTER	TITLE	PROOFING DOCUMENT
						macrosystem using Earth Observation	acknowledged at the end
C	O	17-19 Oct 2016	Community Ecology for the XXI century: from genes to ecosystems	Évora - Portugal	João Pradinho Honrado	Satellite remote sensing of ecosystem function: towards improved prediction and monitoring of biodiversity and ecosystem services	Evora_Honrado_Alcaraz_2016_abstract.pdf
C	P	20 - 23 Oct 2016	8th Congress of the Hellenic Ecological Society (HELECOS-8)	Thessaloniki - Greece	Dimitris Poursanidis	POSTER: USING MODERN EARTH OBSERVATION DATA FOR THE IDENTIFICATION OF THE DISTRIBUTION OF ENDEMIC REPTILES – THE CASE STUDY OF Podarcis cretensis IN THE NATIONAL PARK OF SAMARIA – WHITE MOUNTAINS	Poursanidis-2016_Podarcis cretensis SDM_gr_FINAL.pdf
C	O	25 -27 October 2016	Sfécologie-2016, International Conference of Ecological Sciences	Marseille, France	Ilse Geijzendorffer	Oral presentation: Ecosystem services supply trends in the Mediterranean Basin	Geijzendorffer ES trends abstract 20161024.pdf
C	O	23-28 October 2016	11th International Conference of the African Association on Remote Sensing of Environment (AARSE) 2016	Kampala, Uganda	Abel Ramoelo (CSIR)	Oral presentation: Ramoelo A. Cho. MA. 2016. Estimation of leaf nitrogen concentration using spectrometer data to calibrate sentinel-2 image	CSIR_AARSE_2016_Ramoelo_final.pptx
W	O	26-28 October 2016	EUFAR ESA Workshop on Atmospheric Correction of Remote Sensing Data	Berlin, Germany	Padro, JC; Pesquer, L; González, O;	Oral presentation: Pseudo Invariant Areas	CDomingo_EUFAR.pdf (conference abstract: Abstracts PDF

Event	O / P	DATE	EVENT	PLACE	PRESENTER	TITLE	PROOFING DOCUMENT
					Domingo, O; Cristóbal, J; Pons, X	and their benefits for atmospheric corrections	(Domingo_26-28-oct- 2016_EUFAR_ESA.pdf)
W	O	14-17 November 2016	First “Life-EcoPotential” meeting on “Ecosystem management of protected areas”	Irvine, USA	Ghada El Serafy	Applying ecosystem services concept to optimize protected area management and the issue of inherent uncertainty in future predictions	LIFE_ECO_Agenda_Fin al.pdf
W	O	14-17 November 2016	First “Life-EcoPotential” meeting on “Ecosystem management of protected areas”	Irvine, USA	H. Hummel, J. van der Meer, O. Hummel <i>et al.</i>	Combining parameters on ecosystem functions, related services, and socio-economic drivers, to manage current and assign new protected areas - points of view of different stakeholders	Hummel-Life- EcoPotential-Irvine USA-Nov2016.pdf

C) - Table 6. C - Other Dissemination Events and Actions (WP12.1)

	DATE	EVENT	PLACE	PARTNER	ACTION	PROOFING DOCUMENT
Communication campaign (e.g radio, TV)]	April 8 2016	Festival Internazionale del Giornalismo	Perugia (Italy)	Elisa Palazzi	#EuFactor campaign promoted by the Representation of the European Commission in Italy and the Information Office of the European Parliament in Italy (the ECOPOTENTIAL project as an example)	https://www.youtube.com /watch?v= Q6eT49NGvo http://www.eufactor.eu/
Organisation of a workshop	6 - 7 May 2016	2 nd EARSeL SIG LU/LC and NASA LCLUC joint Workshop “Advancing horizons for land	Prague, Czech Republic	Ioannis Manakos	DEDICATED SESSION: SESSION 4. EO benefits for ecosystem services and human well being.	manakos_etal_WS_Prague_ poster_prefinal.pdf

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	DATE	EVENT	PLACE	PARTNER	ACTION	PROOFING DOCUMENT
		cover services entering the big data era”			Session Chair: Gary N. Geller, Group on Earth Observations. CO-ORGANIZATION of the event.	
Communication campaign (e.g radio, TV)]	May 16 2016	Salone del Libro	Torino (Italy)	Elisa Palazzi	#EuFactor campaign promoted by the Representation of the European Commission in Italy and the Information Office of the European Parliament in Italy (the ECOPOTENTIAL project as an example)	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Q6eT49NGvo http://www.eufactor.eu/ G-Eu-Factor-Ecopotential.pdf
Communication campaign (e.g radio, TV)]	June 24th 2016	Ansa Interview on Ecopotential	Torino (Italy)	Elisa Palazzi	http://www.ansa.it/scienza/notizie/ragazzi/eufactor/2016/06/24/salvare-le-montagne-grazie-alla-potenza-dei-numeri-_9a18c276-d356-4352-b4d3-db6c01a13f94.html	http://www.ansa.it/scienza/notizie/ragazzi/eufactor/2016/06/24/salvare-le-montagne-grazie-alla-potenza-dei-numeri-_9a18c276-d356-4352-b4d3-db6c01a13f94.html
Participation to a workshop	14-16 Feb 2016	Future Earth’s initiative: E3S Extreme Events and Environments: from Climate to Society cross community workshop	Berlin	Antonello Provenzale Mariasilvia Giamberini	Participation to the sessions of the workshop and final discussions. Ecopotential has been presented at two parallel sessions.	E3S-meeting-agenda_Feb2016_version_2016-02-08.pdf E3S-registration-Provenzale E3S-registration-Giamberini E3S-meeting-agenda_Feb2016_version_2016-02-08.pdf

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	DATE	EVENT	PLACE	PARTNER	ACTION	PROOFING DOCUMENT
other	May 31-June 2nd 2016	6. 10th GEO European Projects Workshop 2016: Fostering Open Earth Observation for Europe	Berlin (DE)	Mariasilvia Giamberini and Antonello Provenzale (CNR)	Ecopotential newsletter distributed as well as information on Ecopotential to relevant stakeholders	
other	4-8 July	GEO BON Open Science Conference & All Hands Meeting.	Leipzig, Germany	Carlos Guerra	Ecopotential leaflet distributed to all participants of the GEO BON conference within the conference welcome package	
other	July 2016	UN Secretary General's Report on Sustainable Mountain Development for the EU General Assembly	NY, USA	UNEP	Ecopotential project mentioned in UN Secretary General's Report on Sustainable Mountain Development that was presented to the General Assembly of the United Nations in 2016.	http://www.mountainpartnership.org/fileadmin/user_upload/mountain_partnership/docs/UN%20General%20Assembly%20Report.pdf
Participation in activities organised jointly with other H2020 project(s)]	19 - 23 September 2016	European ESP conference	Antwerpen, Belgium	Simona Imperio, Ilaria Baneschi, Ariane Walz, Alex Ziemba, Valia Drakou, Mihai Adamescu, Ilse Geijzendorffer, Mariasilvia Giamberini	Joint ECOPOTENTIAL-SWOS stand at the conference, including the display of posters, banners, videos and leaflets.	ESP_Conference2016_Stand_Abstract_v.3_CNR.docx Acceptance: ESS-Antwerp-STAND-Ecop_SWOS
other	19 - 23 September 2016	European ESP conference	Antwerpen, Belgium	Simona Imperio (CNR), Ilaria Baneschi (CNR), Alex	Display of information material about the project at the EU stand: posters, videos and leaflets.	Email: EU-Stand-ESP-Antwerp-poster+video

	DATE	EVENT	PLACE	PARTNER	ACTION	PROOFING DOCUMENT
				Ziemba (Deltares), Mariasilvia Giamberini (CNR)		
Participation to an event other than a conference or workshop	30 September 2016	European Researchers' night	Tessaloniki, Greece	IOANNIS MANAKOS, GEORGIOS KORDELAS (CERTH)	Presentation of Ecopotential with a dedicated stand entitled "The satellites in service of Nature" displaying posters, video, banners. Display of the interactive game on ecology prepared by University of Salento. Dedicated presentations to 6 visiting schools and general public; distribution of the leaflet.	draft poster A4_Manakos.ppt Pictures
Participation to an event other than a conference or workshop	30 September 2016	European Researchers' night	Pisa, Italy	Ilaria Baneschi, Mariasilvia Giamberini, Antonello Provenzale (CNR)	Presentation of Ecopotential with a dedicated stand displaying posters, video, banners. Display of the interactive game on ecology prepared by University of Salento. Dedicated presentations to schools and general public; distribution of the leaflet.	Pictures:
Participation to an event other than a conference or workshop	30 September 2016	European Researchers' night	Porto, Portugal	Claudia Santos, Paulo Alves, Salvador Arenas-Castro (ICETA)	Presentation of Ecopotential with a dedicated stand entitled: "Observar a Terra: os satélites na Ecologia" (Earth observation: the satellites in Ecology). Display of a 7min. slides presentation about	Pictures

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	DATE	EVENT	PLACE	PARTNER	ACTION	PROOFING DOCUMENT
					satellites and examples of work in Ecology, for the public in general. Display of ECOPOTENTIAL roll-ups in A0 size in portuguese. And the movie of the ECOP protected areas passing close to the roll-ups.	
Participation to an event other than a conference or workshop	30 September 2016	European Researchers' night	Lecce, Italy	University of Salento	Presentation of Ecopotential with a dedicated stand displaying posters, video, banners. Display of the interactive game on ecology prepared by University of Salento. Dedicated presentations to schools and general public; distribution of the leaflet.	
other	9-13 Oct 2016	ILTER 1st Open Science meeting	Skukuza – South Africa	Antonello Provenzale , Simona Imperio, Mariasilvia Giamberini (CNR)	Ecopotential leaflet distributed as well as information on Ecopotential to relevant stakeholders	
other	17 to 20 October 2016	World Mountain Forum	Mbale, Uganda	Matthias Jurek (UNEP), Bjorn Alfthan (GRIDA)	Ecopotential leaflet disseminated as well as information on Ecopotential included in UNEP mountain leaflet and other relevant communication products presented at this World Mountain Conference	MountainFlyer_screen.pdf – ecopotential is mentioned

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	DATE	EVENT	PLACE	PARTNER	ACTION	PROOFING DOCUMENT
other	9-10 Nov 2016	GEO XIII Plenary meeting	St Petersburg, Russia	CNR, UNEP	Video, leaflets and Poster displayed at the EU – EASME stand	EXHIBITOR VIDEO FORM-ECOPOTENTIAL.xlsx EXHIBITOR POSTERS FORM.XLSX st-peterburg-stand-email
[Web-site]				CNR	website of the project, continuously updated by Simona Imperio (CNR-IGG) and Benedetto Biagi (CNR-IIA)	www.ecopotential-project.eu
Non-scientific and non-peer reviewed publications (popularised publications)]	March 2016	Newsletter release		CNR	CNR-IGG: Newsletter - Publication of the Issue # 1 - March 2016; editor: Mariasilvia Giamberini	ecopotential-newsletter.igg.cnr.it
Non-scientific and non-peer reviewed publications (popularised publications)]	June 2016	Newsletter release		CNR	CNR-IGG: Newsletter - Publication of the Issue # 2 - June 2016; editor: Mariasilvia Giamberini	ecopotential-newsletter.igg.cnr.it
Non-scientific and non-peer reviewed publications (popularised publications)]	Sept 2016	Newsletter release		CNR	CNR-IGG: Newsletter - Publication of the Issue # 3 - August 2016; editor: Mariasilvia Giamberini	ecopotential-newsletter.igg.cnr.it
Non-scientific and non-peer reviewed publications	June 2016	Leaflet		UNEP-GRIDA - CNR	Publication of the Ecopotential Leaflet	Ecopotential-Brochure_screen.pdf

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	DATE	EVENT	PLACE	PARTNER	ACTION	PROOFING DOCUMENT
(popularised publications)]						http://www.ecopotential-project.eu/outreach/brochures
Press release					CNR-IGG: Press release about Ecopotential on the CNR website for science communication "almanacco della scienza" (in Italian). Author: Antonello Provenzale;	http://www.almanacco.cnr.it/reader/cw_usr_view_articolo.html?id_articolo=7348&id_rub=32&giornale=7320 A- Ecopotential_Almanacco.pdf
Press release	August 2016				CNR-IGG: Press release on the GOFC Newsletter - Author: Mariasilvia Giamberini;	http://www.gofcgold.wur.nl/documents/newsletter/GOFC-newsletter_no36.pdf F-GOFC- newsletter_no36.pdf
Press release					CNR-IGG: Press release on the on-line science communication magazine "telegalileo" (in Italian) - Interview to Antonello Provenzale:	http://www.telegalileo.com/2016/06/01/intervista-alla-scienza-monitorare-ecosistemi-con-il-satellite-ecopotential-il-progetto-europeo-da-16-milioni-di-euro/
Video/film					CNR-ISAC - Elisa Palazzi: On Line Video:	http://zon.it/progetto-ecopotential/

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	DATE	EVENT	PLACE	PARTNER	ACTION	PROOFING DOCUMENT
Press release	June 2016				Deltares: Press release on the Deltares website:	https://www.deltares.nl/en/news/ecopotential-researchers-meet-on-the-shores-of-the-wadden-sea/ I-Ecopotential researchers meet on the shores of the Wadden Sea - Deltares.pdf
Press release					ETH (Ana Stritih): Press release on the ETH-Zurich website:	http://www.plus.ethz.ch/research/forschungsprojekte/ecopotential.html E-ECOPOTENTIAL – Planning of Landscape and Urban Systems – PLUS _ ETH Zurich.pdf
Social media					UBT: Twitter account of the project, continuously updated by Yrneh Ulloa	https://twitter.com/ecopotentialprj https://twitter.com/hashtag/ecopotential
Social media					UBT: Facebook page of the project, continuously updated by Yrneh Ulloa	https://it-facebook.com/EcoPotentialProject
Press release					UNESCO (Francesca Santoro): Press release on the Unesco website:	http://www.unesco.org/new/en/natural-sciences/ioc-oceans/single-view-oceans/news/assessing_ecosystem_services_in_the_mediterranean_large_mari/#.V4Sr5JN97_S

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	DATE	EVENT	PLACE	PARTNER	ACTION	PROOFING DOCUMENT
						D-ECOPOTENTIAL _ United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization.pdf O-Assessing ecosystem services in the Mediterranean Large Marine Ecosystem _ United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization.pdf
Press release					CERTH - Ioannis Manakos - interviewed on the on line magazine Deutsch Welle:	http://www.dw.com/el/ (in Greek) Η-Η γιορτή των ερευνητών στη Θεσσαλονίκη _ Περιβάλλον & Επιστήμη _ DW.COM _ 03.10.pdf
Video	Nov 2016	Release of Ecopotential video		UNEP-GRIDA-CNR	Launch of Ecopotential video and publication on Website, You tube and XIII Geo Plenary	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=CWzyzfkxJ9s http://www.ecopotential-project.eu/outreach/video

ECOPOTENTIAL – FIRST PERIODIC REPORTING

SURVEY OF COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

This report is an annex to the first periodic reporting of Work Package 12 of the H2020 R&I project ECOPOTENTIAL (Grant Agreement n. 641762). It is aimed to verify the implementation of the Communication and Dissemination plan (D12.4).

It contains:

5. The list of the communication activities reported in Table 1 of the C&D plan (D12.4) and the status of their implementation
6. The indicators of communication and dissemination performance (Table 2 of the C&D plan)
7. The survey of social media activities
8. The list of conferences and other dissemination events where ECOPOTENTIAL has been presented (either presentations of the projects as a whole and scientific results presentations).

7. List of activities from the C&D plan – status of implementation.

The status of implementation of the actions reported in “Table I: Summary of actions” of the Communication and Dissemination Plan (D12.4) has been checked.

The following actions have been undertaken:

- Project website design, implementation and maintenance with sections targeted at different audiences
- Quarterly newsletter
- Social Media (Facebook, Twitter) accounts setting and maintenance
- Science policy interface and experience sharing events/ communication material
- Standard ECOPOTENTIAL templates for partner use
- Visual tools put online via YouTube/Vimeo, etc.
- Print material (booklets, science papers reprints)
- Project deliverables
- Scientific Publications on Journals
- Presentations at conferences
- Science schools
- Internal communications (discussion board, email, teleconferences)

The actions that still are to be implemented or completed are:

- Photographic and museum exhibitions
- School workshops

- Science-policy study carried out in WP11 with strong communication component
- Citizen Science actions
- Public Discussion Forum
- ECOPOTENTIAL Virtual Laboratory Platform
- Community of practise (CoP)

The communication and dissemination activities undertaken may be summarized as follows (data uploaded in the EU Participant portal – System for Grant Management – Dissemination and Communication activities)

Table 6: Summary of communication and dissemination activities as reported in the EU reporting portal SyGMa

[Organisation of a workshop]	3
[Press release]	7
[Non-scientific and non-peer reviewed publications (popularised publications)]	3
[Flyers]	1
[Training]	3
[Social media]	2
[Web-site]	1
[Communication campaign (e.g radio, TV)]	3
[Participation to a conference]	48
[Participation to a workshop]	22
[Participation to an event other than a conference or workshop]	12
[Video/film]	2
[Participation in activities organised jointly with other H2020 project(s)]	1
[Other]	6

A further detail of the communication activities implementation is reported in the following table (From the C&D Plan – D12.4) and in the list of communication activities in Table 6 at the end of this document.

Table 7: Communication and Dissemination Activities from the C&D Plan

Action/tool	How to implement	Actions taken	Status of implementation	Further Actions
Project website with sections targeted at different audiences	Design, implement and maintain the website.	The website is active and it contains all the pages and information needed.	Actions due up to now implemented accordingly. Further actions will follow.	Update continuously and maintain web site security.
Quarterly newsletter	Quarterly issues to be released using a web content management system (e-mailing) and printed versions to be disseminated at conferences and events.	The CMS has been set up, the mailing list has been created and three issues have been released within the reporting period both via e-mailing and in printed version. A fourth issue has been released in December 2016.	Actions due up to now implemented accordingly. Further actions will follow as scheduled.	Release the newsletter quarterly.

Action/tool	How to implement	Actions taken	Status of implementation	Further Actions
Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	Set the accounts and promote actively the participation of the scientific community.	Facebook and Twitter accounts have been set up and are used regularly for advertising about project's events.	Actions due up to now implemented accordingly. Further actions will follow as scheduled	Set LinkedIn account and ask partners to join it. Continuously update and use the social media. Enforce their use as a mean for disseminating information to the target audience.
Science policy interface and experience sharing events/ communication material	Organize meetings for science and stakeholders communication.	Awareness raising event "Putting mountains on the agenda of Horizon 2020" in Brussels, 25 April 2016.	Actions due up to now implemented accordingly. Further actions will follow as scheduled	Organization additional events at respective fora and platforms in the future depending on opportunities.
Standard ECOPOTENTIAL templates for partner use	Ensure a consistent brand is used by ECOPOTENTIAL partners in presentations and in publications.	A standard template was created and shared with partners for written reports, posters, banners and presentations.	Action completed	
Visual tools put online via YouTube/Vimeo etc	Disseminate ECOPOTENTIAL to different audiences.	Simple Show video produced and showed by November 2016. The Video has been displayed at the EASME EU Stand at the GEO plenary assembly in St. Petersburg, Nov 2016.	Actions due up to now implemented accordingly. Further actions will follow as scheduled	Further develop story maps over 2017 and disseminate the video.
Print material (booklets, science papers reprints)	Print and disseminate the leaflet	Leaflet produced by end June 2016 and distributed to all partners at General Assembly and major conferences and events (GEO BON, ESS, ILTER, Researchers Night)	Action completed	.
Photographic and museum exhibitions	Engage and educate with public exhibitions.	Planning / ideas development to occur in late 2016. Deliverable due month 30.	Due in-2017	To be planned and implemented in year 3 (month 30). Planning starts in late 2016.

Action/tool	How to implement	Actions taken	Status of implementation	Further Actions
School workshops	Educate young generation on the importance of nature to prosperous societies.	Established contacts with selected school teacher groups. Demo version of a scientific game released and tested.	Due in-2017	During the second year, specific activities will be planned and carried out.
Science-policy study carried out in WP11 with strong communication component	Raise awareness about bottlenecks and gaps in terms of integration of EO tools in decision making and management of PAs.	A comprehensive questionnaire was developed to identify the needs of PA managers for ECOPOTENTIAL research outputs, in close collaboration with assigned ECOPOTENTIAL scientific partners. Results are reported in D11.2.	First part of the study has been completed within D11.2.	D11.2, submitted in November 2016, reports the first results of the assessment. The report will serve as basis for the PA meeting in May 2017. Final report by month 42.
Project deliverables	Dissemination of results to wider research and practice communities, use and re-use of outputs.	The available deliverable open to the public are published on the website, section http://www.ecopotential-project.eu/2015-08-19-15-19-29/deliverables .	Actions due up to now implemented accordingly. Further actions will follow as scheduled	Upload public deliverables within one month after submission.
Citizen Science actions	Engage public in conducting science that helps the environment.	A methodology for a research program on citizen science in PAs has been developed for milestone 12.4. The methodology comprises both a survey on citizen science activities in protected areas and a PhD research-project on the potential of participatory research methods (like CS or PPGIS) for the assessment of cultural ecosystem services.	In progress	The milestone M12.4 (methodology for citizen science) has been implemented in month 18. It will be implemented according to WP12 Task 12.3 and D12.9 (month 36).

Action/tool	How to implement	Actions taken	Status of implementation	Further Actions
Scientific Publications on Journals	Disseminate knowledge and results to the scientific community.	10 papers have already been published on journals as an outcome of the project.	In progress	Scientific results will be submitted for publication by all research partners.
Presentations at conferences	Disseminate knowledge and results to the scientific community.	The project's outputs have been presented at more than 50 international events during the first year. The project as a whole has been presented at more than 20 events. Details are reported separately.	Actions due up to now implemented accordingly. Further actions will follow as scheduled	Scientific results will be submitted for presentations and posters by all research partners.
Science schools	Training of young researchers.	1 summer school in La Palma (Spain) 2 summer school in Valsavarenche (Italy)	Actions due up to now implemented accordingly. Further actions will follow as scheduled	2 further science schools scheduled at months 27 and 39.
Public Discussion Forum	Position ECOPOTENTIAL scientists as leaders in the field, engage and educate members of all sectors, provide a channel for Science-Policy interface.	Participation to many of the several forums listed in section 5.2.2. (LTER, LifeWatch, Future Earth, EU-BON).	Actions due up to now implemented accordingly. Further actions will follow as scheduled	Participation to several forums
ECOPOTENTIAL Virtual Laboratory Platform	Provide open and unrestricted access to interoperable ecosystem Earth Observation data and information. Provide web-based services, open archives, scientific models, semantic assets, and analytics services. Contribute to GEO using the GEOSS Common Infrastructure.	Design of VLP architecture. A demo of the VLP prototype has been shown at the project General Assembly at the end of June 2016. First release and prototype of the platform has been released in June 2016. http://ecovrp.geodab.eu/ecopotential-vrp/home/index-dev.html	In progress	An advanced version will be released at the beginning of 3 rd year, the final release is planned during year 4.

Action/tool	How to implement	Actions taken	Status of implementation	Further Actions
Community of practise (CoP)	Develop a link with stakeholders such as PA managers, nature conservation associations, economic sectors and concerned citizen groups.	Close contacts with the PA managers of the PAs in the project. A 3 days workshop has been planned for May 2017. The programme has been established.	In progress	Meeting with the PA managers in ECOPOTENTIAL, to be expanded to the GEO community.
Internal communications (discussion board, email, teleconferences)	Ensure efficient information exchange, mutual support and foster scientific innovation.	Internal communication has been established, regular meetings are taking place and all the tools have been implemented.	Action completed	Partners responsible of the tasks are organising the internal communication due for sharing the duties. Monitor the efficiency of internal communication tools.

8. C&D performance indicators

The number of persons reached by Communication and Dissemination activities has been estimated as reported in the following Table 3, in order to be uploaded in the Participant's Portal SyGMA technical reporting web site.

Table 8: Estimate of the number of persons reached by communication activities

ACTIVITY	INSERT A NUMBER	NOTES
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	1960	Conferences: 9 general presentation + 7 scientific presentations; average 100 people reached per conference (some plenary sessions, some side sessions) WRKSPS=8 general presentations, 7 scientific presentations - average 30 people per workshop + 3*20 science school students
Industry	n.a.	
Civil Society	n.a.	
General Public	1200	5 presentations @ researchers' night - average 200 people per presentation + 200 school pupils in Thessaloniki - no data from tourists of Pas – we need to improve this when we will have more results, maybe with posters at the visitor centers
Policy Makers	184	80 end users (including directors) of PA WP11 survey + (8 @ESP, 8@meeting of Ghada, 8@GEOBON meeting)+ 5% of attendees at conferences (no workshops)
Media	3896	700 from press releases; web: 400 - newsletter: 300 facebook: 1657; twitter: 226 + 548 Eu-factor video visualisations + 65 Ecopotential video visualisations
Investors	n.a.	
Customers	n.a.	
Other	n.a.	

Moreover, monitoring of Success of Communication Tools and Strategies has been planned in the Description of Actions and in the Communication and Dissemination Plan using an array of indicators as reported below. The choice of indicators will be revised in the next update of the C&D plan.

Table 9: Communication indicators as from Description of Actions and C&D Plan

Communication Tool	Metric of verification*	Result
Project website with sections targeted at different audiences	Visitors in each part of the site; Number of pages visited; Referral statistics.	The most visited 18 pages (in brackets the date of issue of the page) are: Partners (24/08/2015), 6781 accessi Mission (19/08/2015), 4285 accessi Contacts (24/08/2015), 3471 Coordination (19/10/2015), 2929 Presentations (06/10/2015), 2654 Mediterranean LME (26/08/2015), 2542 Hardangervidda (24/08/2015), 2399 Har Negev (20/08/2015), 2335

Communication Tool	Metric of verification*	Result
		<p>La Palma and Caldera de Taburiente (21/08/2015), 2154 Posters (19/10/2015), 1890 First ECOPOTENTIAL General Assembly (28/06/2016), 1886 Storylines (30/05/2016), 1886 Camargue (24/08/2015), 1863 Ohrid and Prespa (24/08/2015), 1834 Scientific Advisors (17/09/2015), 1825 Gran Paradiso (24/08/2015), 1774 Publications (30/03/2016), 1726 Deliverables (30/03/2016), 1676</p> <p>Other relevant statistics: (average per month): Number of sessions: 626 (424 users): 17.41% from Italy, 9.42% from Germany, 7.99 from Spain. Page visualisations: 2152; Page/session: 3.44 Session time: 00:03:21 % new sessions: 67.73% (Habitual users: 32.1%).</p>
Quarterly newsletter	Number of non-partner subscriptions for e-delivery.	Subscribers: 299 Partners: 111 (70.6%) Non partners: 88 (29.4%)
Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	Number of followers/members; Number of retweets.	Twitter: 233 Followers, 416 Tweets Facebook: 116 Followers
Research brochures / highlights / policy briefs	Number of downloads.	<p>The brochure and other communication documents have been distributed to partners via the internal communication platform and then the partners distributed the brochure via email / facebook pages, so the information that we have from the website is not complete.</p> <p>Anyway, the “brochure” webpage has been visited 964 times since the date of issue (04/07/2016) to Dec. 31st 2016. We estimate a download for each visit.</p>

Communication Tool	Metric of verification*	Result
Visual tools put online via YouTube/Vimeo, etc.	Number of views / other online metrics (e.g. average time spent watching).	On Facebook, Ecopotential video reached 1168 people. On YouTube, it has been seen 457 times. On Twitter, the video earned 666 impressions.
Print material (booklets, science papers reprints)	Number of print material distributed.	2,000 brochures have been printed. 1,000: partners are distributing them to stakeholders and at public events (e.g. Researchers night). All the attendees at the GEO BON conference in July 2016 received within the welcome package. 1,000: CNR is distributing them at major events including ILTER conference in South Africa. 200 printed copies of the newsletter have been distributed at conferences.
Project deliverables	Number of downloads.	Deliverables have been distributed to partners via the internal communication platform, so and the information that we can extrapolate from the website is not complete. Anyway, since the date of issue (30/03/2016) to Dec 31 st 2016 the deliverable webpage has been visited 1676 times.
External communications	Number of information events.	We counted more than 30 communication events other than presentations at conferences / workshops. The most relevant are: 1 stand at the ESS conference in Antwerp, Sept 2016 1 day of discussion in Ecopotential at the Mountain Forum in Bruxelles, Posters and video displayed at <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Researchers night (4 venues) - EU Stand at GEO Plenary (St. Peterburg, Nov. 2016) - EU Stand at the ESS Conference in Antwerp, Sept. 2016 Interviews released at EU-Factor (communication event of the EU) Press releases on web magazines
Internal communications	Participation in Basecamp.	237 people participate to the internal communication platform (Basecamp).

Communication Tool	Metric of verification*	Result
(discussion board, mail)		Basecamp hosts the following discussion groups: <ul style="list-style-type: none">- General- Coordination team- Communication team- 12 discussion group (1 for each work package)

9. Social Media activities

The Facebook site of ECOPOTENTIAL is operative since October 5th 2015, and in the last 18 months has collected 104 Likes/followers, more than 129 engaged users and a total reach of 1657 people (Fig.1, Fig.2). Major peaks of user engagement were during the 1st General Assembly of the Project, as well as the release of audiovisual material like the brochure, official video, among others. So far the Facebook site does not register negative feedback from its fans. The majority of the fans (67%) are located in Europe, principally Italy, Germany, Portugal and Spain. The remaining half of the fans are users located in many other countries in the world, which proves the impact of the dissemination strategy beyond Europe.

Figure 1. Accumulated frequency of “Likes per day” and “Daily engaged users” in Facebook. The Likes received reflects the number of followers. The Daily engaged users are the number of people who clicked, liked, commented on or shared ECOPOTENTIAL posts on a daily basis. The time period of the graph displays the first 18 months of the project. Major peaks in the activity are visible around the dates of the 1st General Assembly (June 2016) and the release of audiovisual material in the last months of 2016 (October – November).

Figure 2. Daily total reach of the first 18 months of the project. The total reach is the number of unique people who sees the content of the Facebook page on a daily basis.

The Twitter account of ECOPOTENTIAL, under the user @ECOPOTENTIALprj, is active since October 2015. In the last months has tweeted over 400 Tweets and gained 226 followers; it has been included in 30 thematic lists by its followers (Fig.3). The audience of the ECOPOTENTIAL Twitter account is composed by the followers and by their related followers, meaning that the project reaches approximately 1722 people on a daily basis.

The main topics of the followers revolve around these keywords: research, environmental, project, European, observation, university, ecology and remote. Moreover, a network map indicates that some of the most connected users and hashtags to ECOPOTENTIAL are the Horizon 2020 initiative, ESA, #ecosystems services and #remotesensing, among others (Fig.4).

Figure 3. Number of tweets per month in the first 18 months period of the project (Source: TweetStats)

Figure 4. Map of the most connected users and hashtags to the ECOPOTENTIAL (Source: Mentionmapp)

10. Attendance at conferences and other dissemination activities.

ECOPOTENTIAL project and its scientific results have been presented at a number of scientific and public events. All the events and presentations are listed in Tables 4 and 5.A, 5.B, 5.C below, grouped in these three categories:

- Presentations of the project as a whole (in the framework of WP1 – Task 1.3: networking activities)
- Scientific presentations
- Other events and dissemination activities

On the whole, during this first reporting period there have been 47 participation at conferences, 22 at workshops and 11 at other events. The project as a whole has been presented 26 times: at 11 scientific conferences (7 oral presentations and 4 posters) and at 12 scientific workshops (all oral presentations) plus other events. Researchers gave 36 presentations of scientific results at conferences (27 oral presentations and 9 posters) and 10 scientific presentations at workshops. Scientific results were also presented at other events, as other projects' meetings, invited seminars, master courses.

Also, a number of other dissemination activities have been undertaken, as participation at the Researchers' Night, organization of dedicated workshops, press releases, newsletters, videos, and many other web-based communication actions (see Tables 1,2,4). A joint stand with the H2020 project SWOS has been set at the ESP international conference in Antwerp, Belgium, Sept 19-23.

Table 10: Summary of presentations at conferences, workshops and other events.

Event	Ecopotential as a whole - oral	Ecopotential as a whole - poster	Scientific presentations- oral	scientific presentations- poster
conferences	7	4	28	9
workshops	12	0	9	1
other events	3		4	1
<i>Total ECOP presentation as a whole: 26</i>	22	4		
<i>Total ECOP scientific results presentations: 52</i>			41	11

ECOPOTENTIAL: Attendance at conferences

The following tables contain a list of:

- D) Oral presentations (and posters) of the project as a whole
- E) Oral presentations (and posters) of scientific results
- F) Other dissemination activities

B) Table 6. A - Presentations of the project as a whole (oral presentations and posters) – WorkPakage 12.1 (dissemination) + 1.4 (networking)

C = conference

W = workshop

E = other event

P = poster

O = oral presentation

Event	P / O	DATE	EVENT	PLACE	PRESENTER	TITLE	PROOFING DOCUMENT
C	O	June 3, 2015	EU BON General Meetings and Symposium, Cambridge, 1-4 June 2015	Cambridge	Carmela Marangi	ECOPOTENTIAL: improving ecosystems benefits through Earth observation	Marangi-Cambridge-EUBON meeting-1-4 June 2015.pptx
W	O	11-12 June 2015	Towards a sustainability process for GEOSS Essential Variables (http://www.gstss.org/2015_Bari/program.php)	Bari, Italy	Antonello Provenzale	ECOPOTENTIAL: improving ecosystems benefits through Earth observation	Provenzale_Bari_EV_2015.pptx
W	O	15 - 16 June 2015	9th GEO European Projects Workshop	Copenhagen, Denmark	Antonello Provenzale	ECOPOTENTIAL: improving ecosystems benefits through Earth observation	PROVENZALE-GEPW9-NEW.pdf
E	O	23 July 2015	LifeWatch-ECOPOTENTIAL meeting at CNR,	Rome, Italy	Antonello Provenzale	H2020 ECOPOTENTIAL: improving ecosystems	LifeWatch_Roma_2015_Prov.pptx

			Department of Earth and Environmental Science			benefits through Earth observation	
C	O	2-4 sept 2015	Pianeta Dinamico Congresso congiunto SIMP-AIV-SoGel-SGI	Florence, Italy	Antonello Provenzale	Poster: H2020 ECOPOTENTIAL: improving future ecosystems benefits through Earth observation	dynamicplanet_ecopotential.pdf
C	O	21-25 Sept 2015	13th European Ecological Federation (EEF) and 25th Italian Society of Ecology's (SIte) joint conference: "Ecology at the Interface in Rome"	Rome, Italy	Antonello Provenzale	ECOPOTENTIAL: improving ecosystems benefits through Earth observation	provenzale_eef_plenary_small.pdf
C	P	11-12 November 2015	GEO-XII Plenary meeting	Mexico City	EU Commission Booth	POSTER: H2020 Project ECOPOTENTIAL: improving ecosystems benefits through Earth observation	GEOXII-ECOPOTENTIAL.pdf Mexico-Ecopotential.pdf
W	O	14 Nov 2015	IV convegno GPSO – ANP "La fauna del Piemonte"	Cherasco (CN) - Italy	Antonello Provenzale	Cambiamenti climatici e risposta degli ecosistemi (in Italian)	Provenzale_Cherasco.pdf
C	O	19-20 Nov 2015	Rome 2015 – Science Symposium on climate	Rome, Italy	Mariasilvia Giamberini	ECOPOTENTIAL: improving ecosystems benefits through Earth observation	Rome2015-final-SG.pdf
W	O	15 dic 2015	Conference: I sentieri dell'Acqua di Pianosa (in Italian)	Portoferraio (Italy)	Antonello Provenzale	Monitoraggio degli ecosistemi: progetti in corso e prospettive future (Italian)	Provenzale_Pianosa.pptx
W	O	20-21 Jan 2016	EC GEO European Projects Special Biodiversity Workshop	Brussels (BE)	Stefano Nativi, Paolo Mazzetti	ECOPOTENTIAL: Data portals, community portals, platforms, and GEOSS/GCI	ECOPOTENTIAL_WP10_2016-01-20_Brussels.pdf

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W	O	20-21 Jan 2016	EC GEO European Projects Special Biodiversity Workshop	Bruxelles	Antonello Provenzale	ECOPOTENTIAL: improving ecosystems benefits through Earth observation	ECOPOTENTIAL_Brussels_Jan2016.pdf
C	O	17–22 April 2016	European Geosciences Union General Assembly 2016	Vienna, Austria	Antonello Provenzale	ECOPOTENTIAL: improving ecosystems benefits through Earth observation	P_ECOP_EGU2016_Prov.pdf
Organisation of an event	E	April 25 th 2016	Mountains for Europe's Future: Putting Mountains on the Horizon 2020 Agenda (see http://www.chat-mountainalliance.eu/en/about-brussels.html). Plenary session	Brussels, BE	Matthias Jurek (UNEP), Sylvie Motard (UNEP), Piotr Mikolajczyk (GRID Warsaw)	Organized ECOPOTENTIAL side event at the margins of this Conference on mountain research	DRAFT PROGRAMME.pdf Mountains_for_Europe_Future_detailed_programme_v8_incl_Ecopotential.pdf
W	O	April 25 th 2016	Mountains for Europe's Future: Putting Mountains on the Horizon 2020 Agenda	Brussels, BE	Elisa Palazzi	ECOPOTENTIAL: improving ecosystems benefits through Earth observation	Programme: Mountains_for_Europe_Future_detailed_programme_v8_incl_Ecopotential.pdf
W	O	10 May 2016	ENVRI (Environmental Research Infrastructure) Community meeting	Zandvoort, Netherlands	H. Hummel	The role of MARS, EMBOS and EcoPotential (invited lecture)	Hummel - summary MARS EMBOS EcoPotential.ppt
W	O	May 31-June 2nd 2016	10th GEO European Projects Workshop 2016: Fostering Open Earth Observation for Europe	Berlin (DE)	Antonello Provenzale	ECOPOTENTIAL: improving ecosystems benefits through Earth observation	GEPW10_ECOPOTENTIAL_2-Prov-LR.pdf

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W	O	19-21 July 2016	4th SCERIN (South Central and Eastern European Regional Information Network) Capacity Building Workshop (CBW)	Zvolen, Slovakia	Ioannis Manakos	Improving future ecosystem benefit through Earth observation in the SCERIN: the Ecopotential approach (oral presentation)	manakos_SCERIN_ECOPOTENTIAL_web-july-2016.pdf
C	P	11-15 Sept 2016	EMC 2016 – Second European Mineralogy Conference	Rimini (Italy)	Chiara Boschi	Poster: Carbon Cycle and the geosphere-biosphere interactions	Posters_IGG_EMC2016
C	O	9-13 Oct 2016	ILTER 1st Open Science meeting	Skukuza – South Africa	Antonello Provenzale	H2020 Project ECOPOTENTIAL: making best use of remote sensing and in-situ observations to improve future ecosystem benefits	ECOPOTENTIAL2016_ILTER.pdf
C	O	9-13 Oct 2016	ILTER 1st Open Science meeting	Skukuza – South Africa	Antonello Provenzale	GEO ECO: The GEO Global Ecosystem Initiative (Presentation of the GEO-ECO initiative)	Proposal_GEO_ECO_ILTER
C	P	9-13 Oct 2016	ILTER 1st Open Science meeting	Skukuza – South Africa	Antonello Provenzale et al.	POSTER: H2020 Project ECOPOTENTIAL: making best use of remote sensing and in-situ observations to improve future ecosystem benefits	Ecop_ILTER-GENERAL.DEFINITIVO.pdf
E	E	17. Nov. 2016	4th EU BON Stakeholder Roundtable	Berlin, Germany	Carl Beierkuhnlein (UBT); Piotr Mikołajczyk (GRID-Warsaw); Carlos Guerra (IdV)	[Piotr Mikołajczyk - participation in an interactive group discussion on monitoring and forecasting, tools for critical biodiversity assessment.]	participant List EU BON Roundtable v5.pdf (+minutes)
E	O	16 Nov 2016	GIS Day @ University of Bergen	Bergen, NO	Tessa Bargman	ECOPOTENTIAL: improving ecosystem benefits through Earth observation	Bargman_GISdag_No v-2016.pptx

W	O	14-17 November 2016	First “Life-EcoPotential” meeting on “Ecosystem management of protected areas”	Irvine, USA	Antonello Provenzale	ECOPOTENTIAL: improving ecosystem benefits through Earth observation	Provenzale_ECOPOTE NTIAL-Nov- 2016_Irvine-USA.pptx
Organisation of a workshop	E	14-17 November 2016	First “Life-EcoPotential” meeting on “Ecosystem management of protected areas”	Irvine, USA	CNR	Event: Joint Research Meeting ECO-Life	LIFE_ECO_Agenda_Fi nal.pdf
C	P	November 16-17, 2016	LTER-Italy Congress and Assembly, 16-17 November 2016	Mantova (Italy)	Simona Imperio	H2020 Project ECOPOTENTIAL: making best use of remote sensing and in-situ observations to improve future ecosystem benefits (Poster)	LTER_Ecop_GENERAL .pdf
W	O	22-23 November 2016	9 th Regional meeting of the Technical Working Group – Water Framework Directive: From Planning to Acting – Transboundary Water Management Revisited	Tirana, Albania	Orhideja Tazevska	ECOPOTENTIAL: improving ecosystem benefits through Earth observation	PresentationECOP - RTWG Meeting in Albania.ppt

B) Table 6. B - SCIENTIFIC PRESENTATIONS AND POSTERS AT CONFERENCES AND WORKSHOPS

Event	O / P	DATE	EVENT	PLACE	PRESENTER	TITLE	PROOFING DOCUMENT
C	P	23 October 2015	1st International Symposium: What can remote sensing do for the conservation of Wetlands?	Seville, Spain	Pere Serra Ruiz, Alaitz Zabala, Xavier Pons, Javier Bustamante, Ricardo Díaz-Delgado, Antonello Provenzale	POSTER: ECOPOTENTIAL: a framework to monitor ecosystem services in protected wetlands with remote sensing.	Serra Ruiz-RSCW2015-abstract.pdf Available at http://ocs.ebd.csic.es/index.php/RSW/RSCW2015/paper/view/326
C	P	14-18 Nov 2015	AGU Fall Meeting 2015	San Francisco (USA)	Emiliana Valentini, Andrea Taramelli et al.	POSTER: Deltaic margins vulnerability: the role of landscape patches in flood regulation and climate adaptation	Poster_AGU_Fall_2015_v5.pdf
C	O	19-20 Nov 2015	Rome 2015 – Science Symposium on climate	Rome, Italy	Simona Imperio	Climate change effects on the distribution of large mountain herbivores	Imperio_Rome2015 - Science Symposium on Climate_19-20 November 2015.pdf
E	O	December 11, 2015	3rd EU BON Stakeholder Roundtable 10th – 11th December 2015, Granada, Spain	Granada	Carmela Marangi	"EO data for ecosystem modelling and monitoring"	Marangi-Granada-EUBON stakeholder roundtable 10-11 Dec 2015 .pdf
C	O	1-4 March 2016	7th European Coastal Lagoon (ECoLag) Symposium	Murcia, Spain	H. Hummel	Coastal lagoons in the framework of biodiversity observation networks (keynote lecture)	Hummel-March 2016-Eurolag-Murcia Spain-Keynote lecture.pdf Hummel-March2016-Eurolag-Murcia Spain-round table summary.pdf

Event	O / P	DATE	EVENT	PLACE	PRESENTER	TITLE	PROOFING DOCUMENT
C	O	1-4 March 2016	7th European Coastal Lagoons Symposium,, Murcia	Murcia, Spain	Rutger De Wit (CNRS, Montpellier)	Oral Presentation: A. Leruste, S. Villéger, N. Malet, R. De Wit & B. Bec. First use of multidimensional functional diversity indices for phytoplankton in coastal lagoons	Eurolag7.27.02.16
C	O	1-4 March 2016	7th European Coastal Lagoons Symposium,, Murcia	Murcia, Spain	Rutger De Wit (CNRS, Montpellier)	Oral Presentation: R. De Wit. Restoration ecology for coastal lagoons : need for a highly integrated multidisciplinary approach	DeWit_7Eurolag.pdf
C	O	18th-19th April, 2016	NASA LCLUC Spring Science Team Meeting, 2016 (20th Anniversary) - Session – IX. International Partner Programs, Education and Capacity Building	Bethesda, Maryland (USA)	Ioannis Manakos	Earth Observation LULC products in support of Ecosystems monitoring in the EU (oral presentation)	Agenda-LCLUC_Ver.5.6_0.pdf manakos_NASA_LCLU C_springMeeting2016_web_sub.pdf
C	P	18th-19th April, 2016	NASA LCLUC Spring Science Team Meeting, 2016 (20th Anniversary) - Session – IX. International Partner Programs, Education and Capacity Building	Bethesda, Maryland (USA)	Ioannis Manakos	POSTER: Remote Sensing in service of ecosystems and human well-being	Ecopotential_Manakos_etal_NASA_LCLUC_sub.pdf
C	O	17–22 April 2016	European Geosciences Union General Assembly 2016	Vienna, Austria	Ghada El Serafy Sandra Gaytan Aguilar, and Alexander Ziemba	Improving the spatial and temporal resolution with quantification of uncertainty and errors in earth observation data sets using Data Interpolating Empirical	abstract-EGU2016-9454-El-Serafy-21-april-2016.pdf EGU-2016_DINEOF-Ziemba.pptx

Event	O / P	DATE	EVENT	PLACE	PRESENTER	TITLE	PROOFING DOCUMENT
						Orthogonal Functions methodology	
C	O	17–22 April 2016	European Geosciences Union General Assembly 2016	Vienna, Austria	Antonio J. Pérez-Luque et al	Temporal trend of the snow-related variables in Sierra Nevada in the last years: An analysis combining Earth Observation and hydrological modelling	EGU2016-Sierra Nevada-April-2016pdf.pdf
C	O	20–23 April 2016	X Italian Congress of Mammalogy	Acquapendente (VT), Italy	Simona Imperio et al.	Factors affecting demographic parameters of an Alpine chamois population and estimated response to expected climate change	Imperio_Congresso Italiano di Teriologia_20-23 April 2016.pdf
W	O	April 25 th 2016	Mountains for Europe's Future: Side event dedicated to ECOPOTENTIAL	Brussels, BE	António Monteiro	ICETA : “Case study – Peneda-Gerês National Park, Portugal”	Programme: Mountains_for_Europe_Future_detailed_programme_v8_incl_Ecopotential.pdf
W	O	April 25 th 2016	Mountains for Europe's Future: Side event dedicated to ECOPOTENTIAL	Brussels, BE	Ana Stritih	Comparing mountain ecosystem services in protected and non-protected areas: The Swiss National Park and the region of Davos	Programme: Mountains_for_Europe_Future_detailed_programme_v8_incl_Ecopotential.pdf
W	O	April 25 th 2016	Mountains for Europe's Future: Side event dedicated to ECOPOTENTIAL	Brussels, BE	Piotr Mikolajczyk	Case study – High Tatras Mountains, Carpathians	Programme: Mountains_for_Europe_Future_detailed_programme_v8_incl_Ecopotential.pdf
W	P	6 - 7 May 2016	2 nd EARSeL SIG LU/LC and NASA LCLUC joint Workshop “Advancing horizons for land cover services entering the big data era”	Prague, Czech Republic,	Ioannis Manakos	POSTER: Multi modal knowledge based generation from remote sensing very high	manakos_etal_WS_Prague_poster_prefinal.pdf

Event	O / P	DATE	EVENT	PLACE	PRESENTER	TITLE	PROOFING DOCUMENT
						resolution imagery for habitat mapping OPEN ACCESS PAPER (gold): I. Manakos, E. Technitou, Z. Petrou, O. Karydas, V. Tomaselli, G. Veronico, G. Mountrakis, "Multi-modal knowledge base generation from very high resolution satellite imagery for habitat mapping", 2016, European Journal of Remote Sensing, (accepted for publication - to appear).	
W	O	6 - 7 May 2016	2 nd EARSeL SIG LU/LC and NASA LCLUC joint Workshop "Advancing horizons for land cover services entering the big data era"	Prague, Czech Republic	Palma Blonda, ISSIA CNR – Bari	LC taxonomies for applications to biodiversity and ecosystems monitoring	Keynote_Blonda_PRA GA_2016.pdf
C	P	9-13 May 2016	ESA Living Planet Symposium 2016	Prague, Czech Republic	Dimitris Poursanidis	POSTER: Monitoring land cover changes over National Parks with EO to identify ecosystem functions, services and assist biodiversity conservation	POSTER: FORTH_2016_SAMARIA changes.pdf ABSTRACT: LPS16-poursanidis-7-may-2016-abstract.pdf
C	O	9-13 May 2016	ESA Living Planet Symposium 2016	Prague, Czech Republic	Dimitris Poursanidis et al.	Monitoring land cover changes over National Parks†with EO to identify ecosystem functions" services and assist biodiversity conservation	Living Planet Symposium 2016 - ECO POTENTIAL.pdf ABSTRACT-

Event	O / P	DATE	EVENT	PLACE	PRESENTER	TITLE	PROOFING DOCUMENT
C	P	9-13 May 2016	ESA Living Planet Symposium 2016	Prague, Czech Republic	Emiliana Valentini	POSTER and Paper: Marine food provision ecosystem services assessment using EO products	POSTER: 2016_Valentini_et_al_Marine_Food_Provision_ES_using_EO_ESA_LPS2016_1942_poster.pdf
W	O	May 31-June 2nd 2016	10th GEO European Projects Workshop 2016: Fostering Open Earth Observation for Europe	Berlin (DE)	Hermann Hummel	Marine dimensions of European biodiversity and ecosystem observations	GEPW10_Hummel-marine biodiversity observation networks.pdf
E	P	June 2016	DEVOTES-Euromarine Summer School: Marine ecosystem services, management and governance: linking social and ecological research	San Sebastian, Spain	O.A. Hummel	The importance of Ecosystem Functions and Ecosystem Services to enhance the protection level of current and future Protected Areas	The importance of Ecosystem Functions and Ecosystem Services.pdf
C	O	3-8 July 2016.	51th Annual Congress of the Grassland Society of Southern Africa (GSSA)	George, South Africa	Abel Ramoelo (CSIR)	Oral Presentation: Towards earth observation based near-real time estimation of regional grass biomass as an indicator of rangeland quantity: A critical input for determining carrying capacity of herbivores	Biomass - Presentation-AR-Final-ECO.pptx
C	O	4 - 8 July	GEO BON Open Science Conference & All Hands Meeting.	Leipzig, Germany	Palma Blonda	Oral Presentation: A. Adamo, C. Tarantino, V. Tomaselli, G. Veronico, H. Nagendra, P. Blonda. Pattern zonation rules and very high resolution satellite imagery for ecosystem extent monitoring	Blonda_GEO_BON_LI PSIA_4_July_habmapping.pdf - presentation

Event	O / P	DATE	EVENT	PLACE	PRESENTER	TITLE	PROOFING DOCUMENT
C	O	4 - 8 July	GEO BON Open Science Conference & All Hands Meeting.	Leipzig, Germany	Ilse Geijzendorffer, Anis Guelmami, Gaetan Lefebvre, Brigitte Poulin	Oral presentation: Measuring ecosystem services variables in Mediterranean Wetlands	Abstract – OK GEOBON_Abstract_Book_OSC2016.pdf – S6.8
C	O	4-8 July	GEO BON Open Science Conference & All Hands Meeting.	Leipzig, Germany	Carlos Guerra:	Policy impacts on regulating Ecosystem Services	GEOBONconf2016-Guerra.pdf
C	O	4-8 July	GEO BON Open Science Conference & All Hands Meeting.	Leipzig, Germany	Evangelia Drakou	a. Mapping cultural marine ecosystem services from space: fact or fiction?	GEOBON_Abstract_Book_OSC2016.pdf S6 Drakou.pdf
C	O	4-8 July	GEO BON Open Science Conference & All Hands Meeting.	Leipzig, Germany	Domingo Alcaraz Segura et al.	Remotely-sensed Ecosystem Functional Types: monitoring functional diversity at the ecosystem level	Abstract: GEOBON_Abstract_Book_OSC2016.pdf S1.7 – Ecopotential is mentioned Presentation: Alcaraz-Segura_2016_GEOBON_ppt.pdf
C	O	4-8 July	GEO BON Open Science Conference & All Hands Meeting.	Leipzig, Germany	Ana Stritih	Bayesian modelling of mountain ecosystem services: A prototype for avalanche protection	Ana-Stritih-GEO-BON-4-7-2016.docx Abstract-Stritih_GEOBON-4th-july-2016.pdf – presentation
W	O	6-9 September 2015	Estuarine Coastal Shelf Science Association (ECSA 55), London, UK	London, UK	Rutger De Wit (CNRS, Montpellier)	Oral Presentation: R. De Wit, A. Hervé, E. Romet, M. Ribot, J. Picot, L. Foulc, O. Loste, M. Thibault, O. Boutron, P. Grillas, B. Poulin. Offered space for coastal change in S. France; what to do	ECSA_London_presentationDeWIT.pdf

Event	O / P	DATE	EVENT	PLACE	PRESENTER	TITLE	PROOFING DOCUMENT
						with abandoned solar salterns?	
E	O	15 September	Invited seminar at University of Brest	Brest, France	Ilse Geijzendorffer	Oral presentation: Ecosystem services and Sustainable Development Goals	Geijzendorffer SDGs 20160915
C	O	19-23 Sept 2016	European Ecosystem Services 2016 Conference	Antwerp, Belgium	Mariasilvia Giamberini, Ilaria Baneschi, Orhideia Tazevska et al	An Ecosystem Services Approach for the Sustainable Management of Lake Ohrid	ESS-conference-B3-Lake-Ohrid_Giamberini_Tazevska.pdf + email-acceptance
C	O	19-23 Sept 2016	European Ecosystem Services 2016 Conference	Antwerp, Belgium	Domingo Alcaraz Segura et al	Essential social-ecological functions to refine the conceptual framework of ecosystem services	PRESENTATION: Pacheco-Romero_EESC 2016 ppt.pdf (CONTAINS ONLY THE ECOP LOGO) Abstract: Pacheco-Romero_EESC 2016 abstract.pdf
C	O	19-23 Sept 2016	European Ecosystem Services 2016 Conference	Antwerp, Belgium	Arjen Boon, Alex Ziemba	Applying ecosystem services to optimize protected area management	abstract_ecopotential_Sevilla.docx presentation: 04-Boon+ElSerafy.pdf
C	O	19-23 Sept 2016	European Ecosystem Services 2016 Conference	Antwerp, Belgium	Herman Hummel	The importance of Ecosystem Services required to qualify and install Marine Protected Areas – variable views of stakeholders and a comparison with other	The importance of Ecosystem Services required to qualify and install Marine Protected Areas – variable views of stakeholders and a

Event	O / P	DATE	EVENT	PLACE	PRESENTER	TITLE	PROOFING DOCUMENT
						geographic domains http://www.esconference2016.eu/86157/subscribe?survey_id=69574&survey_key=CdjFot17PaYJB3tmg3xqShJODU0MTc0CkxMDAwCnRwMQou	comparison with other geographic domains - Herman Hummel.pdf Abstract
C	O	19-23 Sept 2016	European Ecosystem Services 2016 Conference	Antwerp, Belgium	Ricardo Moreno Llorca	Temporal evolution of ecosystem services in Sierra Nevada (Spain).	Abstract: Temporal evolution of ecosystem services in Sierra Nevada (Spain).pdf
C	O	19-23 Sept 2016	European Ecosystem Services 2016 Conference	Antwerp, Belgium	Simona Imperio, Tessa Bargmann et al.	Dynamics of high-altitude environments as a life-support system to wild herbivores: a storyline from the ECOPOTENTIAL project	Imperio_EESC_2016_low.pptx Abstract_EESC_high-altitude environments_Imperio.pdf
C	O	19 - 23 September	European ESP conference	Antwerp, Belgium	Ilse Geijzendorffer, Carlos Guerra	Oral presentation: Ecosystem services and Sustainable Development Goals	Geijzendorffer SGs abstract 20160919.pdf
C	O	26-30 September 2016	51st European Marine Biology Symposium (EMBS)	Rhodes, Greece	H. Hummel, J. van der Meer, O. Hummel et al.	The role of ecosystem functions and ecosystem services in the protection of protected areas	Hummel-27 Sept 2016-Rhodes Greece-51st EMBS .pdf
E	O	Sep 25-26, 2015	European Researchers' Night (MeetMeTonight)	Milan, Italy	Renato Casagrandi (PoliMI)	Oral presentation: Big Data - Unexpected opportunities for Environment and Health	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9zUSfGL42mQ
C	P	9-13 Oct 2016	ILTER 1st Open Science meeting	Skukuza – South Africa	Simona Imperio et al.	POSTER: Long-term monitoring of two	Ecop_ILTER-2016_ungulates.pptx

Event	O / P	DATE	EVENT	PLACE	PRESENTER	TITLE	PROOFING DOCUMENT
						mountain ungulates in the Alps: ecosystem and cultural services, and impact of global changes	
C	P	9-13 Oct 2016	ILTER 1st Open Science meeting	Skukuza – South Africa	Ramona Viterbi, Mariasilvia Giamberini, Ilaria Baneschi et al.	POSTER: Set-up of a long-term study on the changes in Alpine grasslands owing to climate and grazing pressure modifications	Ecop_ILTER-2016-grassland_DEFINITIVO.pptx
C	P	9-13 October 2016	1st ILTER Open Science Meeting	Skukuza, Kruger National Park, South Africa	Abel Ramoelo (CSIR)	Poster Presentation: Ramoelo A, Cho M.A. Towards earth observation based near-real time estimation of regional grass biomass as an indicator of rangeland quantity	ILTER 2016 KNP Ramoelov2_final.pptx
E	O	11 October	Invited teacher during a master course for practitioners at the Aix-Marseille university	Marseille, France	Ilse Geijzendorffer	Oral presentation: Zones humides Méditerranéens	Geijzendorffer zones humides 20161010.pdf
C	O	11-12 Oct 2016	ISSI FORUM - "Monitoring coastal zones evolution under various forcing factors using space-based observing systems"	Bern - Switzerland	Andrea Taramelli	Oral presentation: Living deltas and use of EO data: investigate a rapidly developing macrosystem using Earth Observation	Presentation: ISSI_Living delta_Bern_11_10_2016_final.pdf – ECOP is acknowledged at the end
C	O	17-19 Oct 2016	Community Ecology for the XXI century: from genes to ecosystems	Évora - Portugal	João Pradinho Honrado	Satellite remote sensing of ecosystem function: towards improved prediction and monitoring of	Evora_Honrado_Alcaraz_2016_abstract.pdf

Event	O / P	DATE	EVENT	PLACE	PRESENTER	TITLE	PROOFING DOCUMENT
						biodiversity and ecosystem services	
C	P	20 - 23 Oct 2016	8th Congress of the Hellenic Ecological Society (HELECOS-8)	Thessaloniki - Greece	Dimitris Poursanidis	POSTER: USING MODERN EARTH OBSERVATION DATA FOR THE IDENTIFICATION OF THE DISTRIBUTION OF ENDEMIC REPTILES – THE CASE STUDY OF Podarcis cretensis IN THE NATIONAL PARK OF SAMARIA – WHITE MOUNTAINS	Poursanidis-2016_Podarcis cretensis SDM_gr_FINAL.pdf
C	O	25 -27 October 2016	Sfécologie-2016, International Conference of Ecological Sciences	Marseille, France	Ilse Geijzendorffer	Oral presentation: Ecosystem services supply trends in the Mediterranean Basin	Geijzendorffer ES trends abstract 20161024.pdf
C	O	23-28 October 2016	11th International Conference of the African Association on Remote Sensing of Environment (AARSE) 2016	Kampala, Uganda	Abel Ramoelo (CSIR)	Oral presentation: Ramoelo A. Cho. MA. 2016. Estimation of leaf nitrogen concentration using spectrometer data to calibrate sentinel-2 image	CSIR_AARSE_2016_Ramoelo_final.pptx
W	O	26-28 October 2016	EUFAR ESA Workshop on Atmospheric Correction of Remote Sensing Data	Berlin, Germany	Padro, JC; Pesquer, L; González, O; Domingo, O; Cristóbal, J; Pons, X	Oral presentation: Pseudo Invariant Areas and their benefits for atmospheric corrections	CDomingo_EUFAR.pdf (conference abstract: Abstracts PDF (Domingo_26-28-oct-2016_EUFAR_ESA.pdf)
W	O	14-17 November 2016	First “Life-EcoPotential” meeting on “Ecosystem management of protected areas”	Irvine, USA	Ghada El Serafy	Applying ecosystem services concept to optimize protected area management and the	LIFE_ECO_Agenda_Final.pdf

Event	O / P	DATE	EVENT	PLACE	PRESENTER	TITLE	PROOFING DOCUMENT
						issue of inherent uncertainty in future predictions	
W	O	14-17 November 2016	First “Life-EcoPotential” meeting on “Ecosystem management of protected areas”	Irvine, USA	H. Hummel, J. van der Meer, O. Hummel <i>et al.</i>	Combining parameters on ecosystem functions, related services, and socio-economic drivers, to manage current and assign new protected areas - points of view of different stakeholders	Hummel-Life-EcoPotential-Irvine USA-Nov2016.pdf

C) - Table 6. C - Other Dissemination Events and Actions (WP12.1)

	DATE	EVENT	PLACE	PARTNER	ACTION	PROOFING DOCUMENT
Communication campaign (e.g radio, TV)]	April 8 2016	Festival Internazionale del Giornalismo	Perugia (Italy)	Elisa Palazzi	#EuFactor campaign promoted by the Representation of the European Commission in Italy and the Information Office of the European Parliament in Italy (the ECOPOTENTIAL project as an example)	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v= Q6eT49NGvo http://www.eufactor.eu/
Organisation of a workshop	6 - 7 May 2016	2 nd EARSeL SIG LU/LC and NASA LCLUC joint Workshop “Advancing horizons for land cover services entering the big data era”	Prague, Czech Republic	Ioannis Manakos	DEDICATED SESSION: SESSION 4. EO benefits for ecosystem services and human well being. Session Chair: Gary N. Geller, Group on Earth Observations. CO-ORGANIZATION of the event.	manakos_etal_WS_Prague_poster_prefinal.pdf

	DATE	EVENT	PLACE	PARTNER	ACTION	PROOFING DOCUMENT
Communication campaign (e.g radio, TV)]	May 16 2016	Salone del Libro	Torino (Italy)	Elisa Palazzi	#EuFactor campaign promoted by the Representation of the European Commission in Italy and the Information Office of the European Parliament in Italy (the ECOPOTENTIAL project as an example)	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Q6eT49NGvo http://www.eufactor.eu/ G-Eu-Factor-Ecopotential.pdf
Communication campaign (e.g radio, TV)]	June 24th 2016	Ansa Interview on Ecopotential	Torino (Italy)	Elisa Palazzi	http://www.ansa.it/scienza/notizie/ragazzi/eufactor/2016/06/24/salvare-le-montagne-grazie-alla-potenza-dei-numeri-_9a18c276-d356-4352-b4d3-db6c01a13f94.html	http://www.ansa.it/scienza/notizie/ragazzi/eufactor/2016/06/24/salvare-le-montagne-grazie-alla-potenza-dei-numeri-_9a18c276-d356-4352-b4d3-db6c01a13f94.html
Participation to a workshop	14-16 Feb 2016	Future Earth's initiative: E3S Extreme Events and Environments: from Climate to Society cross community workshop	Berlin	Antonello Provenzale Mariasilvia Gamberini	Participation to the sessions of the workshop and final discussions. Ecopotential has been presented at two parallel sessions.	E3S-meeting-agenda_Feb2016_version_2016-02-08.pdf E3S-registration-Provenzale E3S-registration-Giamberini E3S-meeting-agenda_Feb2016_version_2016-02-08.pdf

	DATE	EVENT	PLACE	PARTNER	ACTION	PROOFING DOCUMENT
other	May 31-June 2nd 2016	11. 10th GEO European Projects Workshop 2016: Fostering Open Earth Observation for Europe	Berlin (DE)	Mariasilvia Giamberini and Antonello Provenzale (CNR)	Ecopotential newsletter distributed as well as information on Ecopotential to relevant stakeholders	
other	4-8 July	GEO BON Open Science Conference & All Hands Meeting.	Leipzig, Germany	Carlos Guerra	Ecopotential leaflet distributed to all participants of the GEO BON conference within the conference welcome package	
Participation in activities organised jointly with other H2020 project(s)]	19 - 23 September 2016	European ESP conference	Antwerpen, Belgium	Simona Imperio, Ilaria Baneschi, Ariane Walz, Alex Ziemba, Valia Drakou, Mihai Adamescu, Ilse Geijzendorffer, Mariasilvia Giamberini	Joint ECOPOTENTIAL-SWOS stand at the conference, including the display of posters, banners, videos and leaflets.	ESP_Conference2016_Stand_Abstract_v.3_CNR.docx Acceptance: ESS-Antwerp-STAND-Ecop_SWOS
other	19 - 23 September 2016	European ESP conference	Antwerpen, Belgium	Simona Imperio (CNR), Ilaria Baneschi (CNR), Alex Ziemba (Deltares), Mariasilvia Giamberini (CNR)	Display of information material about the project at the EU stand: posters, videos and leaflets.	Email: EU-Stand-ESP-Antwerp-poster+video
Participation to an event other than a	30 September 2016	European Researchers' night	Tessaloniki, Greece	IOANNIS MANAKOS, GEORGIOS	Presentation of Ecopotential with a dedicated stand entitled "The satellites in service of Nature" displaying posters,	draft poster A4_Manakos.ppt Pictures

	DATE	EVENT	PLACE	PARTNER	ACTION	PROOFING DOCUMENT
conference or workshop				KORDELAS (CERTH)	video, banners. Display of the interactive game on ecology prepared by University of Salento. Dedicated presentations to 6 visiting schools and general public; distribution of the leaflet.	
Participation to an event other than a conference or workshop	30 September 2016	European Researchers' night	Pisa, Italy	Ilaria Baneschi, Mariasilvia Giamberini, Antonello Provenzale (CNR)	Presentation of Ecopotential with a dedicated stand displaying posters, video, banners. Display of the interactive game on ecology prepared by University of Salento. Dedicated presentations to schools and general public; distribution of the leaflet.	Pictures:
Participation to an event other than a conference or workshop	30 September 2016	European Researchers' night	Porto, Portugal	Claudia Santos, Paulo Alves, Salvador Arenas-Castro (ICETA)	Presentation of Ecopotential with a dedicated stand entitled: "Observar a Terra: os satélites na Ecologia" (Earth observation: the satellites in Ecology). Display of a 7min. slides presentation about satellites and examples of work in Ecology, for the public in general. Display of ECOPOTENTIAL roll-ups in A0 size in portuguese. And the movie of the ECOP protected areas passing close to the roll-ups.	Pictures

ECOPOTENTIAL – first periodic reporting - Annex to WP12 technical reporting: C&D survey

	DATE	EVENT	PLACE	PARTNER	ACTION	PROOFING DOCUMENT
Participation to an event other than a conference or workshop	30 September 2016	European Researchers' night	Lecce, Italy	University of Salento	Presentation of Ecopotential with a dedicated stand displaying posters, video, banners. Display of the interactive game on ecology prepared by University of Salento. Dedicated presentations to schools and general public; distribution of the leaflet.	
other	9-13 Oct 2016	ILTER 1st Open Science meeting	Skukuza – South Africa	Antonello Provenzale , Simona Imperio, Mariasilvia Giamberini (CNR)	Ecopotential leaflet distributed as well as information on Ecopotential to relevant stakeholders	Pictures
other	17 to 20 October 2016	World Mountain Forum	Mbale, Uganda	Matthias Jurek (UNEP), Bjorn Alfthan (GRIDA)	Ecopotential leaflet disseminated as well as information on Ecopotential included in UNEP mountain leaflet and other relevant communication products presented at this World Mountain Conference	MountainFlyer_screen.pdf – ecopotential is mentioned
other	9-10 Nov 2016	GEO XIII Plenary meeting	St Petersburg, Russia	CNR, UNEP	Video, leaflets and Poster displayed at the EU – EASME stand	EXHIBITOR VIDEO FORM- ECOPOTENTIAL.xlsx EXHIBITOR POSTERS FORM.XLSX st-peterburg-stand-email

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[Web-site]				CNR	website of the project, continuously updated by Simona Imperio (CNR-IGG) and Benedetto Biagi (CNR-IIA)	www.ecopotential-project.eu
Non-scientific and non-peer reviewed publications (popularised publications)]	March 2016	Newsletter release		CNR	CNR-IGG: Newsletter - Publication of the Issue # 1 - March 2016; editor: Mariasilvia Giamberini	ecopotential-newsletter.igg.cnr.it
Non-scientific and non-peer reviewed publications (popularised publications)]	June 2016	Newsletter release		CNR	CNR-IGG: Newsletter - Publication of the Issue # 2 - June 2016; editor: Mariasilvia Giamberini	ecopotential-newsletter.igg.cnr.it
Non-scientific and non-peer reviewed publications (popularised publications)]	Sept 2016	Newsletter release		CNR	CNR-IGG: Newsletter - Publication of the Issue # 3 - August 2016; editor: Mariasilvia Giamberini	ecopotential-newsletter.igg.cnr.it
Non-scientific and non-peer reviewed publications (popularised publications)]	June 2016	Leaflet		UNEP-GRIDA - CNR	Publication of the Ecopotential Leaflet	Ecopotential-Brochure_screen.pdf http://www.ecopotential-project.eu/outreach/brochures
Press release					CNR-IGG: Press release about Ecopotential on the CNR website for science communication "almanacco	http://www.almanacco.cnr.it/reader/cw_usr_view_articolo.html?id_articolo=7348&id_rub=32&giornale=7320

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					della scienza" (in Italian). Author: Antonello Provenzale;	A- Ecopotential_Almanacco.pdf
Press release	August 2016				CNR-IGG: Press release on the GOF C Newsletter - Author: Mariasilvia Giamberini:	http://www.gofcgold.wur.nl/documents/newsletter/GOF-C-newsletter_no36.pdf F-GOF C- newsletter_no36.pdf
Press release					CNR-IGG: Press release on the on-line science communication magazine "tegalileo" (in Italian) - Interview to Antonello Provenzale:	http://www.tegalileo.com/2016/06/01/intervista-alla-scienza-monitorare-ecosistemi-con-il-satellite-ecopotential-il-progetto-europeo-da-16-milioni-di-euro/
Video/film					CNR-ISAC - Elisa Palazzi: On Line Video:	http://zon.it/progetto-ecopotential/
Press release	June 2016				Deltares: Press release on the Deltares website:	https://www.deltares.nl/en/news/ecopotential-researchers-meet-on-the-shores-of-the-wadden-sea/ I-Ecopotential researchers meet on the shores of the Wadden Sea - Deltares.pdf
Press release					ETH (Ana Stritih): Press release on the ETH-Zurich website:	http://www.plus.ethz.ch/research/forschungsprojekte/ecopotential.html

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						E-ECOPOTENTIAL – Planning of Landscape and Urban Systems – PLUS _ ETH Zurich.pdf
Social media					UBT: Twitter account of the project, continuously updated by Yrneh Ulloa	https://twitter.com/ecopotentia/prj https://twitter.com/hashtag/ecopotential
Social media					UBT: Facebook page of the project, continuously updated by Yrneh Ulloa	https://it-it.facebook.com/EcoPotentialProject
Press release					UNESCO (Francesca Santoro): Press release on the Unesco website:	http://www.unesco.org/new/en/natural-sciences/ioc-oceans/single-view-oceans/news/assessing-ecosystem-services-in-the-mediterranean-large-mari/#.V4Sr5JN97_S D-ECOPOTENTIAL _ United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization.pdf O-Assessing ecosystem services in the Mediterranean Large Marine Ecosystem _ United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization.pdf
Press release					CERTH - Ioannis Manakos - interviewed on the on line magazine Deutsch Welle:	http://www.dw.com/el/ (in Greek)

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						H-H γιορτή των ερευνητών στη Θεσσαλονίκη _ Περιβάλλον & Επιστήμη _ DW.COM _ 03.10.pdf
Video	Nov 2016	Release of Ecopotential video		UNEP-GRIDA-CNR	Launch of Ecopotential video and publication on Website, You tube and XIII Geo Plenary	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=CWzyfKxJ9s http://www.ecopotential-project.eu/outreach/video